

Finnish Use Cases 2

Finnish Use Cases

Single-cell RNA sequencing enabling individual disease treatment. The revolutionary single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) measures the activity of all genes separately in each cell, giving a more accurate picture of how cells differ from each other. This technology will produce a vast amount of information on diseases, such as cancer.

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A personal secure computing environment

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ELIXIR FINLAND

Tel. +358 9 457 2821
e-mail: servicedesk@csc.fi

www.elixir-finland.org

www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/nodes/finland

Personalised medicine against cancer and viruses. Modelling cells and simulating how they work gives a boost to personalised treatment plans. The modelling of cells in detail is, however, a major undertaking, requiring a lot of computing power by supercomputers.

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Realisation:
Ari Turunen and
Paula Winter
Up-to-Point Ltd.
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*Teaching an algorithm to identify cancer from sequence data. Deep learning has revolutionised cancer research. Deep neural networks can automatically detect features within a patient's sample data that can be used to identify cancers. In the future, learning algorithms will be able to identify potential early-stage cancers from a blood sample. **Page 58***

Predictive algorithms on supercomputers will accelerate cancer diagnosis and personalized medicine

CSC has now operated a node for 10 years within ELIXIR, the European bioinformatics and life science information research infrastructure. In this book, we present examples of stories featuring leading scientists from Finland and how they collect and use biological data in their work. This science contributes to a broader international narrative on the molecules of life, enhancing our understanding of molecular biology.

CSC needed to develop technical capabilities to manage research data due to the growing number of biological data analysis projects. Impact of this development is the highlight of our journey. In 2013, CSC supported around a hundred computational science projects in health and biological research. By 2023, CSC supported 1,432 projects in health and biological research, including services to facilitate research on data regulated by

ral network on a supercomputer using well-organized and maintained life science data. This achievement is a remarkable scientific milestone, addressing a gap in our understanding of how information stored in genes translates into molecular-level structural details. Such innovations enable, for instance, much more effective virtual screening of new drug candidates.

The research processes described in this book begin with information stored in genes, their translation into functional protein molecules, and finally, the formation of self-organized cellular structures that can be measured with technological advances, such as single-cell measurements. This paves the way for future applications in cancer diagnosis and personalized medicine. The work being done now will help society manage challenges in the future, such as the rising healthcare costs associated with an aging European population. Understanding the molecules of life stored in ELIXIR core data resources is key to addressing these issues.

When well-organized data and substantial computing power converge, exciting developments are inevitable. It is thrilling to consider what will happen within the ELIXIR node and in Finland over the next ten years. CSC now hosts the world's fifth-largest LUMI scientific

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Established in 1971, Finnish ELIXIR Node CSC is a globally recognized organization in scientific computing. CSC played a significant global role in the first Internet “protocol wars,” connecting Finland to the internet in the 1980s. We are a true open source of software for science, including being the first distributor of Linux.

There has been substantial growth in CSC's life science user base over the last ten years.

the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which was implemented in 2018.

It has become evident that access to data and compute environments is increasingly essential for solving scientific problems. The protein folding prediction problem, which puzzled structural biology for 50 years, saw a breakthrough in 2022. With support from protein structure data from ELIXIR core data resources, Google engineers achieved a significant increase in prediction accuracy by training a neu-

ic supercomputer in a consortium of 11 European countries. We aim to integrate ELIXIR core data, such as genomes, images, and bioactive molecular structures, more closely with this computing resource in Finland. This integration will enable European science to achieve more scientific breakthroughs, for example better preparedness for analyzing pathogens such as COVID-19 with a high level of detail. However, based on the number of Finnish academic researchers, there is a natural limit to the number of projects that can be undertaken. Thus, further international growth is likely to stem from an expanding international and industry user base, which the LUMI ecosystem will facilitate. Combined with technology that makes data massively available on European supercomputing platforms, the development of predictive algorithms will accelerate.

The key technology for realizing these advances is the management of security-graded research data in the CSC supercomputing environment. We will need

to bring large-scale data content to computing services, ensuring that high-quality organizational and technical measures are taken to protect it and informing researchers of their roles in the process. Finland cannot achieve this alone, and CSC engages internationally in the development of technical standards, just as we did in the 1980s when the Internet was young. One example of such work is our leadership in establishing a standard for digital identity and access permissions with the Global Alliance for Genomics & Health in 2021. As in the past, the implementation of technical specifications into software and services, making development accessible to end users, is key. In the Finnish research ecosystem, implementation is facilitated by CSC's academic Sensitive Data services, which provides solutions made by CSC also for Statistics Finland (Fiona), the National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), and Findata.

Like GDPR in 2018, the forthcoming European Health Data Space will influ-

ence the ELIXIR node, but we are well positioned to enable Finnish research to adapt to the European digital data governance focusing on compliance and data interoperability standards. With our established infrastructure and experience in managing secure, privacy-compliant data environments, CSC is prepared to facilitate the seamless integration of Finnish research activities into the European Health Data Space (EHDS). This initiative aims to enhance the ethical sharing and research use of health data across Europe, fostering innovation and helping improve future patient outcomes. Our proactive approach to data management, including the adoption of cutting-edge security technologies and adherence to robust ethical guidelines, ensures that Finnish researchers can fully leverage the benefits of the EHDS while meeting all regulatory requirements. By facilitating research and education access to a wider range of high-quality health and biological data and supporting the development of interoperable data platforms, we are enable more effective research that can contribute to the advancement of life science and the delivery of personalized medicine.

Tommi Nyrönen
Director, Head of Node ELIXIR Finland

"In the Finnish research ecosystem, implementation is facilitated by CSC's academic Sensitive Data services, which provides solutions made by CSC also for Statistics Finland (Fiona), the National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), and Findata."

Sensitive data infrastructure

Sharing biomedical data collected of humans is a prerequisite for disease prevention and treatment in the modern world. CSC is building an infrastructure in which human data obtained from Finland's biobanks and research organisations has been pre-processed and described and saved in a secure way. The parties responsible for sharing the data can automate their authorisation process with the CSC platform. This improves licensed availability of data for research and healthcare purposes.

Personalised drug treatments are only possible if patient data is available and it has been stored and pre-processed correctly. In a project funded by the Academy of Finland, an infrastructure is created that meets the requirements for storing and using sensitive data. The data consists of clinical register data, genomic data and material related to bioimaging. The project is participated in by not only CSC but also the bioimaging infrastructure Euro-BioImaging, THL Biobank and the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM).

The project creates solutions to facilitate quick and easy access to various data for by researchers. The data can be stored in CSC's sensitive data infrastructure. Researchers are allocated a space in which the data and computing power are in the same place. Researcher can only access data to which authorisation has been obtained by the data owner. The project also makes use of federated data management developed by CSC. ELIXIR AAI and REMS are applications developed by CSC for the managing users in the ELIXIR infrastructure.

Secure transfer of data will revolutionise healthcare in the next decades.

The project supports researchers developing artificial intelligence algorithms by offering them computing services, more advanced research use of health data, and data management technologies. The data material's compatibility with international standards is also verified.

Secure pre-processing of genomic data security

The sequencing capacity of the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland and Helsinki University Central Hospital is improved with a direct connection to CSC's computing and data services. Genomic data is transferred to CSC on a superfast and secure optic cable. Data pre-processing and quality assurance are fast, because the data is located at CSC.

As the sequence data is physically closer to the computing services, the pre-processed data will be available to the researcher more quickly. The capacity can be used to sequence exomes, genomes and transcriptomes efficiently.

Combining genetic and clinical data still requires a lot of data storage and computing capacity. The European HPC Center

of Excellence for Personalised Medicine (PerMedCoE), a joint project by CSC and the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, brought the data analysis methods of personalised medicine into the super-computer environment. Algorithms developed in the project can significantly reduce the computing time required for analysis. Analysis of genetic and protein data is becoming faster, facilitating and speeding up disease diagnosis and identification of the appropriate treatments. Disease diagnosis by utilising molecu-

lar biology can in future be done within hours or days.

Bioimaging material and artificial intelligence algorithm

CSC, together with the Finnish biobanks, the National Institute for Health and Welfare and Euro-BiolMaging, which operates from Turku, are developing an artificial intelligence algorithm for mining medical data.

Euro-BiolMaging Finland offers image storing services and data services,

such as image collections. Terabytes of images have been stored in the collections, and these can be used as reference data, for example. The material ranges from plankton imaging to cancer cells.

Euro-BiolMaging Finland also offers medical imaging material. Free access to imaging services is provided by six universities and three university hospitals in Finland. These use Open Microscopy Environment (OMERO) services, enabling researchers to view, organise, analyse

Work in the project is divided into four pillars: artificial intelligence algorithms, computing services, research use of health data, and data management technology. Pillars are theme which, when combined, create solutions for the construction of services containing sensitive data. The success of development work is measured by means of three cases worked on in collaboration with ELIXIR, Finnish Biobank Cooperative (FINBB), the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare and the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM).

Breast cancer cell visualised. EOSC Life (European Open Science Cloud) is a project coordinated by the ELIXIR infrastructure with the objective of offering all European researchers a wide selection of bioindustry IT services. Its purpose is to integrate various federal infrastructures and data services. Picture: Guillaume Jacquemet, Turku Centre for Biotechnology, Ivaska Laboratory

and share material from anywhere with internet access.

Use of national biodata for research

At the moment, the transfer and utilisation of genomic data does not work across borders. CSC is developing standards for genomic data technologies (such as GA4GH.org Passport, Cloud, Beacon), which are also relevant outside Europe, such as North America, Japan and Australia. The purpose of the ELIXIR infra-

structure is to adopt global standards for the responsible sharing of genomic data. Europe also has a strong desire to create a federated data security infrastructure for sensitive genomic data. The plan is to create what is known as European Health Data Space (EHDS). The aim is to make biobanks operate in a compatible, federated data infrastructure that transcends national borders. This is connected to the '1+million genomes' and 'Beyond million genomes' projects funded the EU member states and the Com-

mission. In the 'Beyond million genomes' project, CSC is in charge of the technical infrastructure work.

THL Biobank's part in the project is to design management processes for national health data for research. The objective is to enable researchers and students easier access to material in Finnish biobanks. This would also mean that data could be transferred securely from biobanks to CSC's sensitive data environment and sharing it with those who have been authorised to access it.

Sensitive Data (SD) services for research: a personal secure computing environment

SD Connect is a service for collecting and storing sensitive research data during the active phase of a research project while SD Desktop users can directly access and manage that data in a virtual computing environment. The services are accessible via a web user interface, from the user's own computer.

"Once users upload their sensitive data to CSC, these data are always kept encrypted when stored, transferred or processed within our services. Decryption is done only when data is made available for

authorised users within the SD Desktop service", says **Francesca Morello**.

This cloud-computing environment is easy to use. Morello is very enthusiastic about the fact that accessing the work-

space does not require specific technical expertise.

"Researchers can access the workspace with just a few clicks. While SD services are suitable for managing sen-

sitive data from any research field, we are working on further facilitating the use of the services, from fully automating data encryption to streamlining the computing environment customisation.”

The services are available to researchers and students affiliated with Finnish academic organisations, research institutes, and their international collaborators. Using CSC services requires to register a CSC account. While SD Connect and SD Desktop have been designed to facilitate collaboration between organisations, the data is always stored in CSC’s cloud services in Finland.

Human sensitive data and organoids

Seppo Vainio is Professor in Developmental Biology at the University of Oulu, and his research area is organoids. An organoid is a simple and small version of an

organ, grown from stem cells. The study of organoids involves the processing of plenty of sensitive data.

“Organoids can be used to model cellular and molecular changes that are either normal or abnormal in terms of organ functioning. The crucial thing is that researchers have developed methods based on the use of human cells to create cells capable of multiple tasks. These can then be used to channelled in various pathways using developmental biology signals. This means we have methods – recipes, if you like – to make cells do different things, such as create organoids that model the normal development of a kidney. We are able to create development models of these and other organs. We also have methods to create similar genetic changes in human stem cells found in the human genome.”

According to Seppo Vainio, organoid study is a current scientific megatrend. Now

we are able to model human disease processes in a new way. When organoids are combined, we can also experimentally study the interaction of tissues and organs during their formative phase in humans. Organoids are useful in studying human diseases and developing new drugs and treatments.

“We have human stem cell libraries in Europe, and in principle, we could create a stem cell storage of every human being in a biobank. Where necessary, we could then draw on this to create a personal disease model for the study of the health and disease of each person.”

Vainio says that as the goal is to have personalised health technology and data, both the stem cell and cell biobank, we have realistic means of finding out how diseases develop. However, all this requires investments in research. Vainio hopes that the Finnish biobank system could be developed in this direction.

“These services are designed so that they provide researchers and data controllers all the instruments to keep their data safe.”

Data is stored in CSC:s Allas and ePouta platforms. Metadata can be sent outside Finland.

One interesting area involves a type of stem cell called an induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC). Human embryonic stem cells were first grown in the late 1990s, and iPSCs, which are very similar to these, were first generated in 2007. These iPSC lines can be created from, for example, a patient’s skin or blood cells, and they can be programmed to differentiate as desired.

“Because iPSCs originate in individuals, the projects also involve a large amount of processing of sensitive patient material. Our goal is to link observations in organoids better and better into patient records. In this context, the Finnish Social and Health Data Permit Authority Findata offers ways for the utilisation of Finland’s numerous register data system.”

For example, the goal with the FinnGen research project study is to gain a better understanding of disease mechanisms and the development of new treatments by combining genomic and health

data. It contains the genetic data of more than 500,000 Finns. The data is returned, as agreed, into Finnish biobanks, from which it is freely available to researchers. FinnGen has identified a number of genetic variants related to diseases.

“Researchers have modelled variants identified in organoids experimentally in order to study in more detail genetic changes associated with diseases, or pathogenesis. Once this research is later connected to automated drug screening performed with various chemical libraries and biomarkers, the process will create a foundation to accelerate the development of new treatments with organoids.”

Data is controlled by the research organisations

Sensitive data include human personal data, ecological data or confidential data. Processing of personal data is regulated

by the European General Data Protection Regulation.

“The data controller is an organisation or a legal representative who takes all the decisions on how the data is used. With SD services, we aim at providing all the tools for researchers and their organisations to manage the data access during collection, analysis and reuse,” says Francesca Morello.

Processing health or register data for secondary use is strictly regulated by national laws. SD Desktop is a certified secondary use environment that has been audited against Findata (the Finnish Social and Health Data Permit Authority) regulations. In this case, data access and data exports are managed by Findata and by CSC’s helpdesk. According to Morello, these services are designed so that they provide researchers and data controllers all the instruments to keep their data safe but the services remain flexible and user friendly.

The study of organoids is a current scientific megatrend, but it involves the processing of plenty of sensitive data.

Suitable especially for life science researchers

Sequencing, storing and processing genetic sequences is a time consuming process. As a first step, DNA sequences can be uploaded by the sequencing facility

directly into researchers' workspace in SD Connect. The encrypted data can be easily shared with other researchers, via a URL. When the data collection phase is over, researchers can spin up a virtual computer with SD Desktop and analyse

the data stored in SD Connect via data streaming. They can also decide to give read only access to their collaborators from other organisations, for example, to analyse their data together.

When researchers have created their results from their genetic analyses, they can publish their data under controlled access using the Finnish Federated EGA service. In this case, the dataset will be assigned a permanent identifier and the data will be advertised internationally via EGA for reuse. The data remains in Finland while approved researchers can access the data via data streaming using the SD Desktop service.

Only one copy of the same dataset is uploaded to CSC and used during all the different stages of research. The Federated EGA (European Genome-phenome Archive) together with its fully compatible American counterpart dbGAP are the primary global resources for access of sensitive human biomedical data consented for research use.

Fluorescent image of a skin sample, where the nuclei are blue, transglutaminase 3 is green, and IgA antibodies (immunoglobulins) are red. Yellow areas indicate overlapping location of IgA and transglutaminase 3 in the skin.

According to Kaunisto, it is possible that gluten intake leads to altered expression of certain RNA molecules in people with dermatitis herpetiformis. It shows the effect of gluten on the immune system, for example on cellular metabolism or inflammation.

At the same time, it is possible to explore how in celiac disease the immune re-

sponse can spread from a local reaction in the gut to a systemic reaction that spreads to the skin or other organs. In other words, the disease is complex, and this complexity includes immunological abnormalities.

Kaunisto studies immune cells and the immune response to find out why some people with celiac disease develop dermatitis herpetiformis.

“It should be remembered that the gut and the skin have different layers that function in different immunological ways. Dermatitis herpetiformis is a really good target for studying the extra-intestinal symptoms of celiac disease. This information can then also be used to investigate other autoimmune diseases. For example, how can rheumatism start in one place and then spread elsewhere and become systemic?”

Around 10 per cent of people with celiac disease have dermatitis herpetiformis. Celiac disease and dermatitis herpetiformis can be investigated by measuring antibodies in the blood. In people with celiac disease and those with dermatitis herpetiformis, gluten triggers the formation of tissue antibodies.

“Celiac disease is known as an intestinal disease, but it has many other symptoms that are not related to the intestines at all. There may be neurological and skin problems too. Is there a difference in immunity between people with celiac disease and people with dermatitis herpetiformis? How can an immune response spread from the gut to the skin – and why does a rash develop?”

CSC can install new software on CSC’s computing environment SD Desktop at the researcher’s request.

The diagnosis of celiac disease exploits the analysis of antibody levels. Transglutaminases are enzymes that bind proteins together in tissues. High levels of antibodies to transglutaminase 2 (S-tGAbA) suggest the person has celiac disease. Transglutaminase 2 modifies the structure of gluten in the body. This causes the lining of the small intestine to become inflamed and damaged.

The Celiac Disease Research Center in Tampere has conducted a study in which patients with dermatitis herpetiformis who were on a gluten-free diet were exposed to gluten for a short period. Before and during exposure, samples were taken from the small intestine and blood. These samples are studied to find out how gluten affects the expression of RNA in blood cells and the small intestine.

“Although some people with celiac disease have the same serum-based antibodies as people with dermatitis herpetiformis, not everyone will get dermatitis herpetiformis”, says Kaunisto.

“Patients with dermatitis herpetiformis have antibodies to transglutaminase 2, but they also have antibodies to a related enzyme, transglutaminase 3. Transglutam-

inase 3 (TG3) antibodies are also found in the skin, close to the rash, and are thought to be involved in its development. TG3 antibodies are also found in the bloodstream of patients with dermatitis herpetiformis. Although some people with celiac disease also have antibodies to transglutaminase 3 in the bloodstream, not all people with celiac disease develop dermatitis herpetiformis. Why this is so is what we want to solve.”

According to Kaunisto, the research is of great benefit to clinical science.

“For example, if celiac disease is not well managed – the person doesn’t stick to a strict gluten-free diet, say – is there a greater chance of developing extra-intestinal symptoms?”

CSC’s sensitive data services

The study involves analysis of sensitive data obtained from patient’s tissue samples. Patients consented to participate in the study. As this is information subject to the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the data will be processed and used in CSC’s sensitive data services (SD Desktop and SD Connect).

The sequencing has been done in collaboration with the University of Helsinki, and the data is stored encrypted in SD Connect and analysed with SD Desktop.

To avoid the long-term effects of gluten, treatment can begin as soon as possible when celiac disease is detected early. However, since gluten is present in many foods, gluten-free diets are difficult to maintain.

“At the moment, the only treatment is a strict gluten-free diet, but there is also a lot of research underway into pharmaceuticals as possible future treatments. The Celiac Disease Research Center also collaborates extensively with companies developing new potential drugs. Drugs may be able to prevent intestinal and other damage in patients in the future, but initially they will likely be adjunctive therapies alongside gluten-free dietary treatment. A preliminary study carried out in Tampere University found that the experimental-phase drug ZED1227 inhibited transglutaminase 2 activity, and its use reduced gluten-induced intestinal damage in patients.”

Personalised medicine against cancer and viruses

Modelling cells and simulating how they work gives a boost to personalised treatment plans. The PerMedCoE project combines clinical patient data with data related to the operation of genes, proteins and cells. The goal is to develop tools that can be used in precision medicine. The modelling of cells in detail is, however, a major undertaking, requiring a lot of computing power by supercomputers.

Personalised medicine will open up great opportunities in the future. The goal is to be able to combine a patient's clinical data with genetic data to create personalised treatment plans. The PerMedCoE project (HPC/Exascale Centre of Excellence in Personalised Medicine) is working to improve the compatibility of personalised medicine modelling software with next-generation exascale supercomputer systems. Their theoretical computing power is as much as 10^{218} operations per second. The project involves researchers from several European universities and

hospitals, and focuses on four cellular-level modelling software systems based on open source code. Further to working on software development, the research project aims to make precision medicine tools easier to use and compatible with a number of European high-capacity computer centres. "Our aim is that these four software systems could be used in many supercomputers," says Project Manager **Sampo Sillanpää** from CSC – Finnish IT Center for Science. "At the moment this is technically very challenging to implement, because all high-performance computing

environments are unique in terms of their system architecture."

The plan is to achieve seamless operation of software and data masses through jointly agreed technologies. In the PerMedCoE project, this is done by means of workflow software and what is known as container technology. Workflows are used to automate different steps required to analyse data. Further to the actual modelling step, a workflow may involve, for example, data pre-processing and steps relying on results produced by the modelling tool. Container technology can be

used to specify a standardised environment in which scientific software is run in each high-performance computing environment taking part in the project. Once the software code and libraries and settings are placed in the container, they can be transferred from one computer to another.

“The software and data are, in a manner of speaking, packaged in a single box, making it easy to move it from one environment to another. CSC have several container technology experts, so the tools can be transferred from one platform to another,” says Sillanpää.

The COVID-19 disease and different cells’ population behaviours are studied using multi-scale models and single-cell data. MaBoSS is software that enables to simulate populations of cells and to model stochastically (Boolean modelling) the intracellular mechanisms that are deregulated in diseases. PhysiBoSS combines MaBoSS with PhysiCell, open source software for simulating large systems of cells. 3D tissues can be studied on standard desktop computers. With PhysiBoSS scientists can analyse the effect of genetic alterations of individual cells at the population level.

“The containers enable experts to create user-friendly workflows. Workflows in the PerMedCoE project consists of several building blocks, each performing a specific precision-medicine calculation. One building block may pre-process data, a second one carrying out the actual analysis, and

a final one delivering the outcome to the end user. This means that the users may not even have to know how many building blocks the automation contains, but focus on analysing the results.”

Modelling COVID-19 at the cellular level

The usefulness of technologies built in the project is assessed by means of various use cases. Workflows are used to analyse which disturbances may be caused at the cellular level by diseases and how the drugs that have been administered actually work. The models can be used to examine cellular metabolism and signal transmission.

“In PerMedCoE use cases, we make use of publicly available genomic data. Now we can study samples taken from coronavirus patients and look for markers in the genomic data to learn which patient groups are particularly susceptible to the dangerous forms of the disease.”

The project models the skin’s epithelial tissue that reacts to a coronavirus infection by calling various immune cells to work against the virus. This may help to identify patient groups that are susceptible to the serious form of the disease.

“The idea is that we are able to run several models simultaneously for individual patients. This results in efficient analysis of sufficiently large amounts of data, so that the modelling results can be used for personalised medicine,” says Senior Data Scientist **Jesse Harrison** of CSC.

COBREXA.jl:
for the simulation of cellular metabolism at genome-scale

CellNOpt:
for modelling signal transduction networks

MaBoSS:
for stochastic simulations of Boolean models

PhysiCell:
for simulating large systems of cells

COVID19 use case (with scRNA-Seq)

The COVID-19 disease and different cells’ population behaviours are studied using multi-scale models and single-cell data. MaBoSS is software that enables to simulate populations of cells and to model stochastically (Boolean modelling) the intracellular mechanisms that are deregulated in diseases. PhysiBoSS combines MaBoSS with PhysiCell, open source software for simulating large systems of cells. 3D tissues can be studied on standard desktop computers. With PhysiBoSS scientists can analyse the effect of genetic alterations of individual cells at the population level.

How cells work at multiple levels, ranging from the individual cells to large populations of cells? CSC – IT Center for Science and the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), alongside ten other academic and commercial players, kicked off in October 2020 a European Commission Centre of Excellence a project called HPC/Exascale Center of Excellence for Personalised Medicine (PerMedCoE). The project develops cell-level modelling software suitable for high-performance computing. Thanks to high-performance computing, biological data such as genomics and proteomics can be made part of precision medicine, because data can be analysed much faster. Diagnoses, for example, should in future be possible to make within hours or days. PerMedCoE is part of the ELIXIR Finland's development programme.

When modelling the COVID-19 use case, cellular-level RNA sequence data is used. Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) may reveal regular interaction between genes, cell lineages, cellular difference and the cellular frame of reference in its environment.

Another key use case of the project concerns cancer diagnostics. The goal is to create modelling tools for the prediction of cancer tumours and the development of patient-specific treatments. The material has been collected by the Wellcome Institute and the Massachu-

setts General Hospital Cancer Center. The database contains more than a thousand tumour-tissue cell lines.

“The project aims, among other things, to identify new drug combinations that could be useful in cancer treatment,” says Jesse Harrison.

This will hopefully lead to more personalised cancer treatments and faster diagnostics.

“In order for this to become reality, closer collaboration will be needed between high-performance computing centres and medical organisations. This is be-

cause we are talking about large amounts of data, and analysing such large-scale personalised data sets is simply not possible with a desktop computer.”

The results and tools of PerMedCoE are open to all researchers.

“The database contains more than a thousand tumour-tissue cell lines.”

Beating cancer

The EU is funding a number of projects that will enable personalised patient treatment in the future. Cancer is an example of a disease that is extremely individualised, whether it is breast, lungs, liver or prostate cancer.

For example, the Conquering Cancer: Mission Possible programme under Horizon Europe will – according to **Esa Pitkänen**, researcher at FIMM (the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland) – pave the way to future cancer research and treatments. The ambitious programme strives to understand the mechanisms that lead to cancer, to discover methods for early detection of cancers, and to achieve breakthroughs in personalised cancer medicine.

“What is common to all these goals is a versatile and comprehensive use of health data by means of new calculation methods. Artificial intelligence algorithms

based on machine learning have indeed already achieved some encouraging results in terms of, for example, digital pathology. The next leaps will be made by combining various data sources in order to make individualised cancer screening and treatment recommendations,” says Pitkänen confidently.

Within the programme, cancer patients become active participants in cancer treatment development, for example by being able to send their health data securely to researchers. This also gives the patients new research data about their own illness.

“It is important that as treatments develop, people are given an equal opportunity to benefit from new treatments regardless of their background. I am glad to see that this has been taken into account in the programme’s recommendations. There is also special emphasis on cancers among children and young people.”

MicroRNAs may reveal type 1 diabetes

MicroRNAs are short RNA strands, of which more than 2,300 have been identified in humans. Their abnormal expression contributes to the development of many diseases, such as cardiovascular and immunological diseases and cancer. Researchers at the University of Turku discovered a microRNA that may be an early indicator of the risk of developing type 1 diabetes.

Professor **Laura Elo** and her research group for computational biomedicine at the University of Turku are developing tools for the diagnosis and treatment of complex diseases, such as diabetes, cancer and rheumatoid arthritis. The group screens patient data using computational methods to find signs of diseases and their risk factors.

Elo, Research Director at the Turku Bioscience Centre, is mining patient data for various biomarkers that may help pre-

dict the onset of diseases or tell something about the response to treatment. A biomarker is a feature that indicates a change in a biological state, in genes or proteins, for example.

Finland - highest incidence of type 1 diabetes in the world

The onset mechanisms of type 1 diabetes have been investigated for a long time in Finland. Type 1 diabetes is caused by the destruction of cells that produce insulin.

The pancreas does not produce the insulin hormone needed by the body, causing the blood sugar level to rise.

“We aim to predict as early as possible which children will get type 1 diabetes.”

Finland is the ideal country for this type of study, because the country's type 1 diabetes incidence is the highest per capita in the world.”

Both genetic and environmental factors play a role, and Elo's group is seek-

Beta cells produce insulin in the Langerhans islets of the pancreas. Insulin is a hormone that reduces the blood glucose levels significantly.

ing biomarkers from diabetics in order to learn something about the development of the disease.

Data is obtained from a variety of sources. One key data set consists of fol-

low-up studies of children. It was already in 1994 that Finland began an ambitious and extensive research project called "Diabetes, Prediction and Prevention" (DIPP) to predict and prevent diabetes. Blood samples collected in the project are studied to discover factors contributing to type 1 diabetes. Children with a genetic risk of developing diabetes are invited to a follow-up study.

"With the parents' consent, the children are monitored since their infancy until they either get diabetes or turn 15."

Samples are taken every 3 months, and from the age of 2 onwards, every 6 or 12 months. The university hospitals of Turku, Tampere and Oulu are taking part in this screening.

Markers searched from blood samples

Samples have also been taken from children who undergo seroconversion at some point. Seroconversion means that autoantibodies begin to appear in the blood. Some of these children develop the disease. The follow-up study includes children with a genetic risk of falling ill.

"The majority of these children never fall ill nor develop autoantibodies. Our goal is to predict as early as possible which children will develop the disease. This is why we study both those who fall ill later and those who remain healthy throughout the follow-up period.

At some point, some children develop autoantibodies, indicating that the body is attacking itself, resulting in the destruction of the beta cells in the pancreas. This can be measured in the follow-up samples," says Elo, but reminds that a large percentage of the children monitored never fall ill nor develop autoantibodies.

The method is to compare the samples of children who have fallen ill to samples from healthy children with as many similarities as possible. The method uses blood samples, and the idea is that blood also reflects disease processes in other

"Thanks to this comparison, Elo's research group found a promising biomarker, a specific microRNA."

In one of their studies, the research groups of Laura Elo and Riitta Lahesmaa analysed RNA sequencing data that enabled the identification of genes related to the progress of type 1 diabetes in patients with a recent onset of the disease. Gene expression is a process in which DNA is copied to RNA (transcription) and RNA is used to produce proteins (translation). The interactions between proteins may be disrupted, causing diseases. The network in the image shows interactions between proteins related to diabetes. The image shows the proteins whose gene expression has changed statistically during the first year of follow-up after the onset of diabetes. The colouring indicates the extent of the change. The STRING database is a collection of protein-protein interaction networks (string.db.org).

parts of the body. In the case of diabetes, for example, it is difficult to get samples from the pancreas.

Thanks to this comparison, Elo's research group found a promising biomarker, a specific microRNA.

"MicroRNAs are very short RNA strands that can be considered epigenetic regulation – they regulate the operation of cells without coding the proteins. MicroRNAs can be identified in the blood."

MicroRNAs have been linked to various diseases, such as diabetes. When comparing various samples, the study discovered a microRNA (6868-3) that seems rather promising.

"We compared the different sample groups to find microRNA associated with falling ill and not falling ill during the follow-up period. In this case, one microRNA clearly appeared to be linked with falling ill."

This result was studied in more detail in laboratory tests.

"We were able to identify this marker in our material at a very early stage and, in fact, predict earlier than with the currently used markers who will eventually fall ill and who will not."

Calculation method for diseases that develop over time

Laura Elo emphasises that the computational methods her group have developed are also suitable for the study of diseases other than diabetes.

"We have also analysed, for example, protein levels in various autoimmune diseases and cancers. A diagnosis is not usually made until clinical symptoms have appeared. In the development of the computational methods, we are motivated by the fact that with the aid of long-term follow-up measurements, we can find very early markers for diseases."

Elo says they have begun to realise even better that it is not worth taking just a single measurement.

"Follow-up studies create, over time, a kind of reference of the person, ena-

"The goal with our method is to discover as reliable markers as possible in longitudinal materials, and the focus was on protein measurements."

bling us to follow changes in the body, and to learn more about disease processes. The marker may be a molecule that is associated with a disease. MicroRNA is one example of such marker."

According to Elo, future study of diseases should make use of the various 'omics', such as genomics (DNA), proteomics (proteins), transcriptomics

(RNA) or metabolomics (metabolism). Elo's group has been using the computing resources of Finland's ELIXIR Node CSC to process the extensive data.

"We recently published a new longitudinal modelling method in the Nature Communications journal.

The goal with our method is to discover as reliable markers as possible in longitudinal materials, and the focus was on protein measurements. One of the key questions was how to reliably analyse noisy data. We compared previously-used methods and got good results in both simulated and real data. We are now able to more reliably find proteins associated with diseases, for example."

Going to the laboratory to confirm findings is a long and expensive process, which is why it is important to find reliable changes and markers.

Discovered biomarker (6868-3b) which can indicate diabetes.

GTACGTACCGT
GTACCGTAACTC
CGTAACTGGTAC
TATTCGTAAGTC
TAACTCCTGGAT
GAAGTCTTGACC
TAGGTCTCCTGA
GTACGTACCGT
GTACCGTAACT
CGTAACTGGT
TATTCGTAAG
TAACTCCTG
GAAGTCTT
TAGGTCT
GTACGTAC
GTACCGTAACT
CGTAACTGGTACTC

Help from the Finnish genome for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases

Professor Samuli Ripatti's group at the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland and the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Helsinki studies the underlying mechanisms of cardiovascular diseases through genetic variation. The genetic heritage of the Finnish population provides a good opportunity for this.

In Finland, there are about 40 hereditary diseases that are characteristic of the Finnish population. The illnesses included in the disease heritage are caused by certain mutations that are more common in Finland than elsewhere in the world due to the so-called bottleneck effect. In the last 10,000 years, a relatively small number of settlers have moved to the Finnish territory. The individuals of this new population represented small and narrow genetic material, resulting in the regional enrichment of certain disease gene variants.

The bottleneck effect is beneficial today for determining the genetic heritage of diseases.

"Finland is the largest bottleneck population on the European scale. Few people have moved here over millennia. The genetic variants that have come to Finland with these immigrants can be a hundred times more common in Finland than elsewhere. This is not often the case in more admixed populations. In Finland, permanent settlements were first established in closer to the coastal areas and only much later in the east and in the north", says **Samuli Ripatti**.

According to Ripatti, the internal migration that took place in the 16th century was a second bottleneck thanks to which large differences are discernible

in the Finnish population between the east and the west. Although population isolate also exist elsewhere, defining the genetic background of the Finnish disease heritage has also inspired investigations of other diseases.

"We are now able to understand the onset principles of many genetically inherited diseases, allowing the research data

"Defining the genetic background of the Finnish disease heritage has also inspired investigations of other diseases."

to be applied elsewhere. Although the diseases are different, they have genetic mechanisms that operate in the same way. Understanding this dynamic is a big thing and may provide new opportunities

for developing new treatments."

For example, when studying Parkinson's disease, it is possible to determine whether the disease is more common in some parts of Finland. If this is the case, research into these parts of the country may produce new genetic information.

Genetic variation of populations

Ripatti is interested in population genetics and genetic variation in Finns. He has been a Professor of Biometry at the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Helsinki since 2013. Biometry is a field of statistics that focuses on the analysis of biological data. Ripatti's research group combines statistical methods with sequence-level measurements of the human genome.

“Those with high cholesterol levels can be examined and their genomes sequenced in an efficient and easy manner.”

“Sequencing provides information on genetic variation, which may be rare in a population. Based on variation, it is possible to see the prevalence of certain genetic changes that modify disease risk in some areas of Finland or demonstrate predisposition for a certain illness.”

This allows the screening of valuable information about the health effects from the population’s genetic data. People at a high risk of getting sick can be found while also looking for ways to prevent diseases.

“We look at this from the point of view of diseases which touch many individuals. We study illnesses that are common in Finland, such as cardiovascular diseases and diabetes.”

Even though these diseases are affected by, for example, diet and other lifestyle choices, hereditary factors are also significant. That is why these conditions are referred to as common complex diseases. Thanks to the Finnish bottleneck effect, Ripatti’s group has identified genetic variants, genes that predispose you to cardiovascular diseases, in particular, and predictive and marker-controlling genes measured in blood. Ripatti uses high cholesterol levels as an example.

“Those with high cholesterol levels can be examined and their ge-

nomes sequenced in an efficient and easy manner.”

Cardiovascular diseases are the cause of one in three deaths in the world. The most affected areas are Central Asia and Eastern Europe. In the 1960s, Finland was the world leader in coronary artery disease mortality of middle-aged men. Upon entering the 2000s, men’s mortality had fallen to about one fifth of the highest level.

However, regional disparities in cardiovascular disease morbidity and mortality are high in Finland. The incidence of the diseases is much lower in Western and Southern Finland than elsewhere in the country. This large regional difference is of interest to researchers. So-called silenced genes that protect against diabetes and cardiovascular diseases have been found in the population of Western Finland.

Silenced genes

One interesting area of study is a gene being turned or becoming inoperative. Such genes are referred to as silenced genes. A study led by Professor **Aarno Palotie** analysed over 80 mutations silencing an entire gene that are rare but more common in Finland than elsewhere in the world. The material was obtained from the genomes of more than 30,000 Finns.

In fact, Finns have more genes that silence the function of an individual gene than other populations.

“Gene variants that disrupt protein production are generally quite rare in human populations. However, the gene variants that disrupt protein production brought to Finland with settlers are more common here than in the rest of Europe and that is why studying the health effects of those variants that

arrived here at that time is much easier in Finland than elsewhere.”

Gene knockouts whose inoperability does not cause health problems have been found in the population of Western Finland. On the contrary, they protect their carrier against diabetes or cardiovascular diseases.

“A gene variant that protects against diabetes has been found in Finland. Carriers of the variant have less incidence of diabetes compared to others. There are more carriers of the gene variant in Ostrobothnia than elsewhere in the world. This may benefit the pharmaceutical industry if it is possible to mimic the function of such a gene through molecular preparations.”

Another example is a gene that prevents the function of lipoprotein(a). Heart disease risk can be assessed by measuring lipoprotein(a) in the blood. Lipoprotein(a) or

LPA is a member of the lipoprotein family that carries LDL cholesterol. The data contained, for example, genetic variants whose carriers lacked lipoprotein(a) produced by the LPA gene almost completely. People lacking lipoprotein(a) develop cardiovascular diseases less frequently than others.

“There are a few variants of the LPA gene that shut off its function. In such cases, there is less lipoprotein(a) in the blood. This results in less vascular disease. Lowering the protein level by pharmacological means would be possible and this could be beneficial in preventing coronary artery disease.”

The function of the USF-1 gene has also been studied in Finland. In humans, the gene affects blood fat levels and cholesterol. When the function of the gene was knocked out in mice, the level of the good HDL cholesterol in the blood increased.

Over-representation of some genetic variants is observed in populations that have experienced a bottleneck. A small population has less genetic variation in the first place.

Cholesterol narrows veins.

“The sequenced sample material has been collected from Finnish patients and volunteers. The material has been used to calculate statistics on how prevalent each genetic variant is in Finland. Once a large enough database has been compiled, it is possible to determine what Finnish genomic variation is like in general.”

FinnGen records the genomes of half a million Finns

The FinnGen project that will record the genomes of half a million Finns. The project utilises samples collected by all Finnish biobanks. The data from genomes is combined with the information in national health care registers.

“Tools for risk assessments exist and statistical models have been developed for several diseases. Interpreting the data obtained from the genome as part of routine health care is the goal of the next few years. FinnGen contributes to this.”

Ripatti and his team participate in the development, implementation and testing of statistical algorithms.

“We develop prediction algorithms that evaluate, for example, the risk of cardiovascular diseases in a patient. We combine genomic data and lifestyle factors, based on which a prediction is made. Therefore, we are looking for ways to motivate the patients to change their lifestyles.”

Ripatti’s group also supplements genomic data with statistical algorithms.

Due to Finland’s population history, it is possible to predict the missing genotypes in microarray data better and more precisely here than almost anywhere else in the world. The algorithm works well in Finnish data because Finnish genomes are on average more alike than elsewhere. Sequence data is used to computationally supplement data collected using gene microarrays.

“The algorithm works well in Finnish data because Finnish genomes are on average more alike than elsewhere.”

“If a gene microarray scanning the essential variation points has 500,000 genetic markers and we know 30 million genome variants of gene sequences in addition to these measurements, we can supplement the measurement done using the gene microarray into a full genome sequence with good statistical quality indicators. This allows the creation of more sufficiently reliable full genomes at a low-

er cost. For the time being, sequencing the entire genome is considerably more expensive.”

Data analysis environment needs improvement

Preserving genomic data in the future and designing its analysis environment are big issues in which the ELIXIR infrastructure plays a key role.

“We have an existing pool of data that can be used by authorised researchers. With large databases, it is necessary to provide researchers with a secure and efficient data analysis environment where the data can be analysed.”

Due to data protection, the best solution would be, for example, a remote desktop. At present, there are hundreds of copies of the population data of different countries on the disk servers of various research groups around the world. It is an enormous amount of data.

“On the other hand, in the future, we must have solutions suitable for analysing genomic data that enable the efficient and decentralised storage and analysis of enormous data sets. This challenge will not be resolved by the closed remote desktop solutions developed previously for much more modest data volumes. Instead, what is required are open computing environments that efficiently utilise cloud services and international cooperation. Considering this is quite essential.”

Hundreds of genes could lie behind a single disease

Professor Aarno Palotie from the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM) focuses on genetic analysis of diseases by utilising large quantities of data gathered from subjects.

Together with Palotie's research team, he has been able to use data analysis to demonstrate that the underlying causes of various neurological diseases consist of numerous genes, instead of a single genetic mutation. For example, there are hundreds of different genes that affect a person's predisposition to migraine, epilepsy, Parkinson's disease or Alzheimer's disease.

Aarno Palotie's research requires an enormous number of samples. In 1998, while working as a professor at The University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA), he had access to the most extensive research data on migraines, available at the time: the data had been collected from 400 Finnish families suffering from migraines. Over the years, the research data has grown and now covers 1,600 families. Between 2007 and 2013, he carried out research related to migraines, schizophrenia and epilepsy in Cambridge, UK, using extensive research material.

Clinical and research data collected on people is constantly being produced and recorded. The more data there is available for research use, the easier it is to find statistical variables. Extensive amounts of data have the potential of revealing new information if the data is mined and analysed well.

"Studies should be able to utilise sample sizes, that are no longer measured in thousands but in millions," Aarno Palotie notes.

"The large sample sizes have been collected from the diverse donor base of different biobanks. Data from different sources is combined in order to really increase the numbers. This way we can increase the signal and reduce the noise."

By increasing the signal, Palotie refers to making the data statistically significant. For example, mining rare diseases from the research material requires large amounts of data.

It is valuable for researchers if the data has been collected using the same methods. Different laboratories and research facilities may have different practices for collecting, processing and classifying raw data from measuring instruments. The more consistent the data is, the easier it is to analyse.

"The more consistent the data is, the easier it is to analyse."

DNA microarrays.

“However, in real life, absolute harmonisations in disease research is very challenging to achieve. That is why it is important to harmonise the aspects that can be harmonised, in order to make real discoveries and correct interpretations using vast quantities of data.”

Cost efficient genotyping

Genome data has conventionally been collected using sequencing techniques that are used to investigate the base sequence of genes in test tubes. However, sequencing costs are very high if a lot of data is required for the study, such as research into common or chronic diseases. Genotyping has become established as a cost efficient and reliable method. In genotyping, a DNA microarray technique is used to collect genetic data from DNA samples. The samples are studied with a microarray scanner and the collected raw data is then processed. Only the sections of chromosomes known to feature genetic variants related to the studied disease are studied in genotyping. After collecting the data, computational methods are put into use. A reference genome (a reference assembly created using DNA sequences from various donors) can be used to predict the variants that were not examined earlier.

The genetic variants that are studied in genome wide association studies (GWAS) are measured from sample sizes varying from hundreds of thousands to

millions of samples. The GWAS method is most commonly used when the genetic background of a disease is multifactorial, or polygenic, meaning that hundreds or thousands of genetic variants affect the disease risk. Multifactorial diseases include cardiovascular diseases, allergies, diabetes and mental disorders, for example. An extensive amount of research data is required for a reliable GWAS analysis. The computing power of super computers is needed to analyse the data.

“Sequencing requires even more extensive amounts of data than GWAS techniques do. Sequencing is also expensive compared to the GWAS method. Producing data using the GWAS methods costs a few dozen euros. The method can be used with extensive enough sample materials. Data is standardised, and it preserves well. Data genotyped at different locations can be easily combined.”

The source of migraine

Migraine is a disorder that causes headaches and is usually considered to stem from a disturbance in the brainstem caused by external factors. One in ten adults suffer from migraines and it is three times more common in females than males. Palotie has studied migraine for a long time. One study utilised samples collected from 375,000 people worldwide. 60,000 of them suffered from migraines. In 2016, his research team identified 30 new hereditary risk

“Even if a variant identified in Finland is unknown in Japan the physiology and biology of people is still very similar.”

factors related to migraine. Many of them are located in genes that regulate vascular function.

In 2018, an article that provided new information on the causes of migraine, written by Palotie and other researchers, was published in the *Neuron* scientific journal. A significant observation was that migraine is not only affected by certain genes, but a vast number of genes. Palotie talks about gene load.

“For decades, the genetics of diseases have been thought of the way Mendel described them. It is actually far more complex,” Palotie says.

Gregor Mendel, who has been called the father of genetics, demonstrated that certain characteristics of a person are inherited by the succeeding generation. Genes can be dominant or recessive. According to Palotie, new research results have shown that it is not that simple. For example, a disease may be affected by a group of genetic mutations, not necessarily only one genetic variant.

“The assumption has been that if there is migraine, heart attacks, cancer or another common condition in the family, the genetic variants that cause it are strong and transferred to children from their

parents. The migraine study together with other research actually show that the cause of certain diseases is likely to be an accumulation of very common genetic variants. These are some of the same variants that can be found in the entire population. Sometimes however, a person and their spouse simply happen to both have a heavy genetic variant load. When these two gene loads, which contain thousands of genetic variants, come together the risk of disease in their offspring increases.

Palotie and his team also search for similar gene loads related to other neurological diseases. Palotie is currently work-

“Genetic findings are believed to play a significant role in understanding diseases and forming a basis for developing new treatments.”

ing on an extensive international study on the genetic background of psychotic disorders. Research material for the study is being collected from over 100,000 people worldwide. Genetic findings are believed

to play a significant role in understanding diseases and forming a basis for developing new treatments.

“If there is a sufficient amount of data available on patients it is possible to provide more specific treatment, this is referred to as targeted treatment or more individualised treatment.”

Rare genetic variants provide a short cut for biology

Palotie conducts his research from two different perspectives: he looks for both accumulations of common genetic mutations and rare genetic variants.

“Rare variants may provide a short cut to biology,” he says.

As an example, Palotie mentions a patient with schizophrenia who had a few genes with a strong mutation connected to the disorder. This is very rare with schizophrenia, because predisposition to the disorder is usually the result of a combined effect of thousands of genes.

“However, such a rare occurrence may reveal something about the mechanisms of the disorder. It may be easier to identify a cell’s biological signaling pathway by studying rare mutations in the genes

of patients with schizophrenia than it is by studying accumulations of common variants.”

Studying the signaling pathway, or understanding how a cell reacts to communication, plays a key role in understanding disease mechanisms. Cells react to messages they get from their surrounding environment. Often the signal goes all the way to the nucleus and starts to regulate what the gene does. Sometimes cells contain special proteins that are there to stop the signal. For example, cancer cells do not react to many signals intended for them. Instead, cancer cells enhance the

Dopaminergic neuron.

signaling pathway, which makes the cell divide and grow.

Finns have a number of genetic variants that are rare in other parts of the world but rich in Finland because of our demographic history. When data collected from Finnish people is combined with data from other populations, we can get more information on signaling pathways. This means that a Japanese patient may benefit from data collected from Finnish patients and vice versa.

“Even if a variant identified in Finland is unknown in Japan the physiology and biology of people is still very similar.

Hopefully, the identified variant helps steer toward the correct cell signaling pathway. When we identify a new cell signaling pathway another genetic variant, that is in-fact connected to the same signaling pathway, may be discovered from another population base. In such case, the finding helps confirm that the signaling pathway is significant in relation to this disease.”

The location of the genetic variant matters. Palotie has an example of this. When visiting Iceland, Palotie talked about **Leif Groop’s** study, as a result of which a rare genetic variant, that protects

from type II diabetes, was discovered in the population on the west coast of Finland. Leif Groop’s colleague asked Icelandic researchers whether a similar variant had been identified in the Icelandic population. The Icelandic researchers checked their databases. The same genetic variant had not been found but there was another variant of the same gene.

“This Icelandic discovery confirmed that the gene in question protects against type 2 diabetes. Such a protective genetic variant is obviously very interesting from the perspective of molecular drug design.”

Rare genetic disorders: Understanding the mechanisms behind even more common diseases

The population in the north of Finland has a unique genetic background. This has enabled the study of rare diseases and the discovery of new genes, proteins and reaction paths.

Docent **Reetta Hinttala** from the University of Oulu and **Johanna Uusimaa**, Professor of Pediatric Neurology, have discovered mutations in the NHLRC2 gene as a cause of a severe childhood multi-organ disease. Currently, the function of NHLRC2 in cells is unknown, but it has been identified as crucial to embryonic development.

“We named the disease FINCA (Fibrosis, Neurodegeneration and Cerebral Angiomatosis) based on the main findings in the patients’ tissues. This is the first time when mutations in the NHLRC2 gene have been identified as a primary cause of a human disease,” says Hinttala.

Reetta Hinttala studies hereditary neurological childhood diseases at the University of Oulu’s Faculty of Medi-

cine. The children suffering from FINCA disease were found to have previously uncharacterised connective tissue formation in their lungs, degeneration of neuronal cells, and increased angiogenesis in the brain. The disease manifested at the age of two months, and progressed quickly.

“Since this was a new combination of symptoms, we suspected that it must indicate a new disease,” says Reetta Hinttala.

The patients’ exomes, i.e. genomic areas encoding proteins, were sequenced. Based on what we currently know, the majority of variants that cause diseases are within those areas that only cover around 1.5% of our genome.

“Exome sequencing revealed changes, variants, in the nucleotide order of the

NHLRC2 gene. At that time, this gene or its variants had not been linked to any human disease or even described in scientific publications. So we started studying the protein encoded by the gene, particularly focusing on its function in cells.”

Help from the mouse model

When you want to find out how a disease emerges and develops in humans, the only way of doing this is to study it in living organisms. Only then can we monitor what the protein that causes a disease is doing in the organism. In this particular case, we created a mouse model with the same mutation combination as the patients. A knock-out mouse, in which the NHLRC2 gene has been completely turned off, was obtained from the

EMMA repository of the Infrafrontier infrastructure. EMMA (The European Mouse Mutant Archive) archives genetically modified mouse strains from around the world. In addition to this, Hinttala and her team used the CRISPR-Cas9 technology to create the identical point mutation that was observed in FINCA patients, to the mouse. By crossing the mouse carrying point mutation with the knock-out mouse, a model was created that has the same mutation combination as the FINCA patients.

“We are using our mouse model to determine the role of NHLRC2 in the development of the central nervous system in particular, through a project funded by the Academy of Finland. At tissue level, we have observed encouraging signs that the mouse model is exhibiting features similar to the FINCA disease, but it will still take some time to build a comprehensive picture of the phenotype.”

Cellular changes resulting from disturbances in the gene causing the disease were studied in the patients’ fibroblasts, using a transmission electron microscope, at Biocenter Oulu’s electron microscopy core facility. Fibroblasts are the main cell type present in connective tissue and they are specialized in secreting extracellular matrix proteins.

“The first indication that a mutation, or variant, is harmful is when the variant changes the protein’s amino acid code. In the patients of our study, mutations of the NHLRC2 gene indeed changed the code. Using cultured fibroblast from patients’ skin biopsies, we checked the expression of the NHLRC2 protein. Fibroblasts from healthy persons’ skin biopsies had a normal level of NHLRC2 protein whereas, owing to mutations, the protein had been almost completely eliminated in the FINCA patient derived cells. This would indicate that the mutations change the

structure of the NHLRC2 protein so radically that the cell attempts to break up the harmful protein. This enabled us to ensure that these were not neutral variants.

“Since this was a new combination of symptoms, we suspected that it must indicate a new disease.”

As a result, the study discovered a gene that was necessary to normal embryonic development. The researchers drew the conclusion that the gene is vital during the first cell divisions in the mouse. Findings in FINCA patients also showed that the NHLRC2 protein plays a key role in maintaining a normal function of several organs in humans.

In FINCA disease, mutations in the NHLRC2 protein cause severe tissue fibrosis and degeneration of nerve cells. Cell culture models can be used to study the role of the NHLRC2 gene in the emergence of nervous diseases. The image shows a cell culture model used to study the effects of the FINCA mutation on developing nerve cells in particular. The cell model consists of neural progenitor cells (NPC) isolated from fetal mouse brain. The effect of the mutation on nerve cells is studied by comparing nerve cells isolated from a FINCA mouse to those from a wild type mouse. These cells can also be modified by gene transfer. Some of the cells in the picture are colored green, because they express green fluorescent protein (GFP), that has entered them through gene transfer. The cell culture contains both transgenic and non-transgenic cells. The red color, on the other hand, indicates neuron-specific form of tubulin protein, which appears normally in all nerve cell cytoskeletons. DNA-binding dye has stained the nuclei of all the cells blue.

Researchers solved the crystal structure of NHLRC2 (Biterova et al. 2018).

“Reaction paths are either turned on or off, depending on the function of the cell.”

Cellular signalling paths provide valuable information

The study of rare diseases may also lead to discovering the causes of more common diseases, specifically proteins with previously unknown mechanisms.

“By studying a rare disease, there is a high probability that we will discover reaction paths that play a role also in more common diseases.”

Cell functions are based on biochemical reactions. Reaction paths are either turned on or off, depending on the function of the cell. Cells change their behaviour on the basis of messages they receive from their environment. For example, when a hormone attaches to a receptor on the cell surface, the receptor activates a certain molecule inside the cell, which will carry the signal further. The signal often ends up in the nucleus and controls the reading of genes. There are large numbers of signalling paths. Cancer cells, for example, do not react to many of the messages intended for them. In-

stead, they strengthen signalling paths that cause the cell to divide, and therefore help the tumour to grow.

The NHLRC2 protein has an effect on many cell reaction paths and events. For the first time, researchers were able to show that a dysfunction of NHLRC2 leads to changes in the cytoskeleton and the formation of vesicles within cells. The cytoskeleton plays a major role in multiple cell functions, and without it the cells would not be able to survive.

According to Hinttala, the study of rare diseases can result in discoveries that are important to basic cellular biology. It is also valuable to learn how dysfunction of genes and proteins manifests in humans.

“With FINCA, a dysfunction of the NHLRC2 protein will result in serious tissue fibrosis and degeneration of neurons. More common diseases, such as liver cirrhosis and Alzheimer’s, have similar tissue manifestations.”

According to Hinttala, the study of rare diseases involves a high probability of discovering the reaction paths that also lead to more common diseases.

“Severe childhood diseases are rarely caused by environmental factors, but the role played by such factors complicates the study of the adult-onset disease mechanisms. The diseases we are studying are most probably hereditary and primarily caused by a dysfunction of a single gene.”

VEIL.AI: patient data in a veil

Patient data is important for research. Personal data is protected by hiding or modifying identity attributes, while maintaining the level of statistical data significant for research purposes. This is enabled by a new, AI-based service.

VEIL.AI anonymises patient data better and faster than traditional methods, and retains information more effectively. If necessary, the application can also produce synthetic, fully anonymous statistical data, which cannot be traced back to any individual.

Developed by the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM), the application is now available for the ELIXIR infrastructure, alongside which a joint service is now being developed. An organisation managing data can protect it by entering the related metadata into a scalable cloud service. The service disguises any identity attributes, providing researchers with anonymised and, if necessary, synthetic data.

Aided by artificial intelligence

The VEIL.AI application employs a model based on artificial intelligence. The application creates a veil that protects the patient's identity attributes, but can identify relevant data, which it keeps.

“Occasionally, for example when creating machine-learning models, more data is required—and more quickly—than research ethics committees tend to allow. They require justification for each variable, which is against the essence of machine-learning where maximum amount of variables is wanted without, a priori, assuming too much of their impact as far as the best mode is still being sought,” says commercialisation expert **Tuomo Pentikäinen**.

This is why, according to Pentikäinen, it makes sense to use synthetic data in the early stages of modelling, as this is what the VEIL.AI method can produce.

“This means data which is totally detached from the people it was derived from, but which, in terms of the desired variables, behaves like the original data. However, synthetic data is only one type of data we provide. Usually customers want anonymised data.”

VEIL.AI can find variables regarded as sensitive in terms of revealing a person's identity, and anonymise them automatically.

“In a better and more organised way, the application can perform heavy calculations and operations concerning the

calculation of data partitioning and anonymisation metrics.”

It must be possible to protect sensitive patient data, but many traditional anonymisation models also lose important data in the process. Traditionally patient data has been protected by partitioning and generalising identity attributes within the data. Anonymisation studies how variables divide/partition data into different groups. Then each group is examined separately, and if some variables are too easy to identify, they are coarsened. Generalisation means that a person’s age can be rounded off by a few years and a professional title can be changed from, say ‘nurse’ to ‘health care professional’.

“So any variables that are too easy to identify are generalised to a sufficiently general level, or perhaps even removed completely. When processing health data, deletion may have to be used quite often if a variable is unique or too easily identifiable,” says Pentikäinen.

This means that generalisation can result in the loss of important patient data.

“This tends to happen when an interesting phenomenon (such as an illness) is relatively rare and fairly evenly distributed across the data set. When such data is divided into partitions for anonymisation, it is common for the phenomenon

of interest to be even rarer in each partition. In cases like this, traditional methods commonly interpret the interesting data as “outliers” in each partition, and therefore remove it. This is stupid, because with a better chosen strategy, the phenomenon of interest could have been included in the partitions, while retaining important information more effectively.”

Timo Miettinen, Information Systems Manager at the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland, has an example: a patient with a rare type of breast cancer.

Creating data that is too coarse can lead to the disappearance of data on the rare type of disease, because there are so few such patients in the data set.

“A breast cancer patient has one diagnosis, but her genetic profile indicates that she has a rare type of breast cancer. There may be a few cases like this per hospital, meaning that they may be classified as outliers and deleted. But this does not apply to the entire population. If a better view could have been gained of the big picture, this outlier would not have been deleted.”

Biobank samples. Picture: FIMM

The biobank samples are stored in Meilahti, Helsinki, in the vapor phase liquid nitrogen at minus 180 degrees Celsius. The National Institute for Health and Welfare was the first to test the process, based on ELIXIR AAI's federated authentication and licence management, using sensitive material from their biobank samples.

Picture: FIMM

"Certain things are difficult to change, such as height, eye colour and place of birth. They are identifiable through statistical methods. The same applies to a person's medical history," says Miettinen.

"We make two promises. First, we promise scalability and better performance. We are able to make use of continuously updated data from a number of sources. We can anonymise this effectively and securely. Our second promise is to try to minimise data loss. The application takes account of the data content, while fulfilling the anonymisation criteria," says Miettinen.

loss of information, while nevertheless achieving the desired level of anonymity," says Pentikäinen.

And crucially, in terms of data security, the VEIL.AI application does not store patient data in a new location.

"We do not want to manage data. Instead, data is streamed through our service, during which we anonymise it and return it immediately to the customer," says Tuomo Pentikäinen.

"We offer a scalable cloud service. Through the user interface, we can enter the necessary data dictionary and teach the algorithm to create the data anonymisation model using example ma-

"The VEIL.AI application uses a neural network that can be thousands of times faster than conventional methods."

Timo Miettinen has been involved for a long time in designing information systems that make use of and protect clinical data. Miettinen and his team have developed the VEIL.AI application, which is about to become commercially available. This micro service was created due to GDPR.

Each biobank in Finland has its own code register. The code register consists of personal identity codes and a synonym table, used to create an identifier—that is, a pseudonym—for each person.

Scalable cloud service

The VEIL.AI application uses a neural network that can be thousands of times faster than conventional methods.

"Our system enables safer data distribution, because once the neural network has been taught what to do, each owner of confidential data can anonymise data before passing it onto its partners. Our method also produces better data, because we can test a huge number of different data partitioning strategies and pick the one that results in the smallest

material. The algorithm will learn to process the data, and if more data is added, it is streamed through the cloud service and anonymised," says Timo Miettinen.

This means that organisations no longer have to share any of their sensitive data with anyone. Data arrives anonymised from the cloud service for research purposes.

The analysis of various pseudo identifiers requires plenty of processing power, which has been obtained from the ELIXIR infrastructure.

“Nordic countries and specifically Finland have a unique opportunity and setting, since they have been collecting health and demographic data for years.”

Risk assessment of cardiovascular diseases for all citizens

Cardiovascular diseases are the most common cause of death in the world. More than a third of deaths in Finland are caused by cardiovascular diseases. The current objective is to create an assessment, based on health data, of each person's risk of illness before they consult a doctor.

Andrea Ganna, EMBL Group Leader from Finnish Institute of Molecular Medicine and instructor from Harvard Medical School, wants to establish a nationwide, personalised risk assessment as foundation for planning public health interventions. The assessment is based on the health, demographic and genetic information of the citizens. The assessment, which uses artificial intelligence, improves

the allocation of preventive treatments with a lower cost than today.

“Nordic countries and specifically Finland have a unique opportunity and setting, since they have been collecting health and demographic data for years. But the way they have used this data in the past is somewhat outdated. Only very specific correlations and associations in the data have been looked at. However, new meth-

ods, such as AI, are emerging, which now allow us to push for a much bigger and ambitious vision.”

Andrea Ganna and his group is developing artificial intelligence (AI) approaches to model health trajectories.

“You have a certain health trajectory and have taken certain medication. We ask if there are other people who have followed a similar path. There may be

Finnish school children. Probably the most important population is younger individuals who do not see a doctor very often. Genetics is particularly valuable because it can capture disease risk at an earlier age than other risk factors. The FinnGen study will utilise samples collected by a nationwide network of Finnish biobanks. The study is based on combining genome information with digital health care data from national health registries.

thousands out there. We leverage those people and ask what happened to those? Let's take that experience and bring it back to you to help you to reduce your disease risk. We can use all this data in a more comprehensive way to help public health and give more information to patients and doctors for decision-making."

Risk assessment before visiting a doctor

Andrea Ganna is interested in epidemiology, genetics and statistics. He has been focusing on leveraging large-scale epidemiological data sets to identify socio-demographic, metabolic and genetic markers of common, complex diseases. In Boston he worked with large-scale exome and genome sequencing data.

According to Ganna, cardiovascular diseases are ideally suited for analysis by artificial intelligence.

"Accurate identification of individuals at high risk is one of the cornerstones of primary prevention of cardiometabolic diseases," he says. "However, at the moment, risk factor assessment for cardiometabolic diseases requires patients to go to the doctor for lipid measurement."

Lipid is the umbrella term used for all fatty acids or their derivatives that circulate in the blood. The body stores fats from food for later use. A diet rich in fats will cause them to attach to the walls of the arteries, leading to cardiovascular and arterial diseases. Lipid measurement is effective, but some members of the population are unaware that they belong to a risk group.

Ganna wants to revolutionize primary prevention by providing risk assessment before an individual even steps into the doctor's office.

"Some simply don't go to the doctor's and so lots of people are missed. However, since all the data on medication and diagnoses has already collected, we can identify high-risk patients without them going to doctor. We can make a risk map of cardiovascular diseases of the whole country by including every individual."

Calculating the risk is done by modelling longitudinal histories of diseases and medications with the gene data, family and demographic data.

"We are trying to understand how genetics interact with data regarding medications, diagnoses, demographics, and familial risk. This can provide an unprecedented holistic view of an individual's health status."

Ganna gives an example.

"When you break your leg, you go to the doctor. However, today the doctor is just

looking at the leg, although during the same visit other information could also be obtained. We can inform the doctor about other risks the patient has based on the collected data. We can precompute the other risks of the patient, for example if this patient has also high risk for cardiovascular diseases. Thus, during the visit, the doctor can also give advice or refer the patient to a specialist.”

Genetics is useful

Ganna chose to come to Finland because of the large genetic project, FinnGen. The FinnGen project will record the genomes of half a million Finns. The project, launched in August 2017, utilises samples collected by all Finnish biobanks. The data from genomes is combined with the information in national health care registers. FinnGen is one of the very first personalised medicine projects of this scale and the public-private collaborative nature of the project is exceptional.

“Finland also has a favourable legislation, giving access to nationwide population data. For me, this is a unique setting”, says Ganna.

ture disease risk at an earlier age than other risk factors,” says Ganna.

“The first step is to understand how people perceive this information. We have to ensure that doctors use the data in a right way and what can be done with it. Cardiovascular diseases are good example, since their treatment is preventive.”

Deep and machine learning

Ganna aims to integrate national and regional registries with deep and machine learning.

“Traditional methods have an advantage since they are relative simple and easy to interpret, but they simple do not scale. In the past 20 years, more than 500 million medical diagnoses have been made of Finns. We are talking about huge data sets. Every year there are millions and millions of new medication purchases and diagnoses. To scale and to leverage this massive data, deep learning methods are needed.”

Artificial neural networks are efficient machine learning algorithms, which can be used in pattern recognition. Recurrent neural networks can use their internal

ample they are used to predict the next most likely word in a text message.”

Deep learning methods need large supercomputing infrastructure.

“CSC has created a secure environment for this computation. Without a secure supercomputing environment, we could not carry out this project. To be successful, we need, on one the hand, research and development, and, on the other hand, a powerful computing environment.”

Personal data is protected

Patient data is important for research, but personal data is also protected. For example, VEIL.AI application created by FIMM anonymises patient data better and faster than traditional methods, and retains information more effectively. If necessary, the application can also produce synthetic, fully anonymous statistical data, which cannot be traced back to any individual.

“We need to guarantee individuals’ privacy but, at the same time, we need to integrate a lot of personal data to really leverage the power of artificial intelligence/deep learning approaches to better target public health interventions. Gen-

Health trajectories might allow to identify individuals at high risk for cardiometabolic diseases when using information available nation-wide.

Ganna and his research group integrate registry-based information with genetic information from large biobank-based studies (e.g. FinnGen) to help identify groups of individuals that can most benefit from existing pharmacological interventions.

“Probably the most important population is younger individuals who do not see a doctor very often. Current risk factors do not work well in this group. Genetics is particularly valuable because it can cap-

memory to process sequences of inputs. This makes them applicable to tasks such as unsegmented recognition. Ganna wants to expand long short-term memory recurrent neural networks to data.

“You can imagine the sequence of health events that we are trying to model as “text” in which each word is a different disease, medication, sociodemographic event etc. across the lifetime. These are naturally suited to model the sequential happening of events, for ex-

erating synthetic health trajectories will help to respect privacy and, at the same time, to combine a lot of personal information within Finland, but also across Nordic countries.”

“My hope is that personal data that is routinely collected in healthcare can help and benefit everyone. My hope is that that this information can help doctors to make better decisions, but also help patients in motivating life style changes. Thus everyone is helping everyone.”

A dog can smell diseases

Metabolomics involves the study of the body's metabolic products, also known as metabolites, and their structure and operation in cells, the blood and secretions. The key issue is understanding the significance of metabolites and their effect on human wellbeing and health. Soile Rummukainen is using metabolomics to study canine and human cancers. Her goal is to identify olfactory molecules related to cancer.

A multidisciplinary research project was started between the University of Helsinki's Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Wise Nose, Aqsens Health Ltd. and the University of Eastern Finland. First, the dogs are trained to identify signs of canine mammary tumours from urine samples. According to tests, sniffer dogs' results were good, with cancer detection of almost 100 per cent. This method will now be extended to detecting prostate and breast cancer.

Dogs have an extremely acute sense of smell. An average-size dog has up to 220 million olfactory receptors, compared to just 5 million in humans. This means that dogs' sense of smell is thousands of times better than that of humans. A mass spectrometer used for the detection of organic matter generally needs some ten billion molecules before anything shows in the reading. A dog can smell out a disease from a much smaller number. In a test conducted at the University of Eastern

Finland, Kössi only needed a sample with ten molecules.

Dogs' findings analysed with mass spectrometer

Metabolites are compounds of low molecular weight that are involved in various cell metabolism functions. These small molecules cannot be seen or detected directly. Instead, you need measuring devices, such as mass spectrometers, which create signals for subsequent analysis.

Soile Rummukainen, an early stage researcher at the School of Pharmacy at the University of Eastern Finland in Kuopio, uses a mass spectrometer to study cancer samples sniffed out by dogs.

"We study these cancer samples and control group samples by using the non-targeted metabolomics method. The mass spectrometer will reveal tens of thousands of molecular features of metabolic products in urine samples. We

use statistical methods to compare differences between groups, trying to identify the most interesting metabolites, that is, those that are different between groups."

With a mass spectrometer and liquid chromatography, it is possible to separate the compounds from the sample and create a mass spectrum for each of them. The x-axis indicates the ion mass formed by the molecules, and the peak height (y-axis) their relative abundance. On the other hand, the molecular fragmentation product is used to determine the molecular structure. Liquid chromatography (LC) combined with mass spectrometry (MS) is an efficient analysis technique for the definition of metabolites. LC-MS methods are used extensively in pharmaceutical research and clinical diagnostics.

Difficulty of metabolite identification

According to Rummukainen, the difficult part of metabolomics is the identification of molecules. You have to be able to identify the molecular structure that corresponds to the fragmentation spectrum. Fragmentation ions are compared to global databases, their fragmentation spectrum library and our own standards.

"Our own standard library consists of standards we have analysed at the university. These will enable us to identify metabolites with maximum accuracy, since they have been analysed using the same methods and analytical devices and include retention time data, which is a key identification component. However, our library is limited, so we must also use other databases."

The retention time refers to the time it takes for the compound to travel through the chromatography equipment to the detector.

A mass spectrometer used for the detection of organic matter generally needs some ten billion molecules before anything shows in the reading. A dog can smell out a disease from a much smaller number. In a test conducted at the University of Eastern Finland, a dog only needed a sample with ten molecules.

"If we get a positive signal from a dog, we will take a closer look at that particular fraction and ignore the rest."

"A biological sample may contain thousands of metabolic products. When we analyse a sample with a mass spectrometer, we get data that results in tens of thousands of molecular features. These features must then be combined into molecules. By means of the exact mass, fragmentation spectra and retention time, we can perhaps identify 100 or 200 metabolites from the sample, which is quite a small number."

That is where the dogs come in again. We move on to fractionating, that is, taking

partial samples from samples. Then we use the dogs to test whether the smell is still present in the fractions.

"If we get a positive signal from a dog, we will take a closer look at that particular fraction and ignore the rest. According to untargeted data, there are statistically significant differences between the metabolic products of those with cancer and healthy individuals."

Rummukainen points out that most work is involved in making and analysing the fractions.

"In the future, we will study these partial samples and analyse the compounds they contain using mass spectrometer methods and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy. With the aid of sniffer dogs and mammary tumour samples, our goal is to create a method that can also be applied to determine metabolites related to human cancers."

Dogs are currently trained to sniff out prostate and breast cancer.

"The related research can help us find new biomarkers for cancer. They may help us to develop new methods for diagnosing prostate and breast cancer, for example."

Data processing is also important. Processing raw data obtained from a mass spectrometer requires plenty of computing power and disk space.

"A single metabolite may be linked to a dozen of intracellular signal routes. In this respect, we would benefit from computer simulation to improve our understanding of the biological significance of any changes identified. It would also be interesting to combine data obtained through genomics and proteomics with metabolomics, once the necessary software and tools become more advanced."

Mass spectrometer measurement data. The image at the top shows a total ion chromatogram (all ionised compounds at any given time point). Before the data is processed, the image cannot be used to distinguish between ions that provide information useful in examinations and those that do not. Software is used to convert raw data into a data matrix. Researchers refer to 'peak picking'.

After peak picking, data analysis and statistical processing, the information of which compounds are important can be obtained. In this case, the information of those metabolites which differ between cancer samples and control samples.

The lower image is from a single time point (retention time 4.03 min.) which shows those mass ions which were detected by the spectrometer at just that moment.

The data matrix includes the combined retention time and ion mass data, as well as the ionic abundance or area of this molecular feature.

Once the most interesting compounds have been identified from the data, the software can be used to find them in these graphs. In addition, fragmentation spectra are needed in order to identify the compounds.

All breast cancer risk factors evaluated with AI

Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer in women. One quarter of all cancers in women are breast cancers. Until now, genetic risk factors for breast cancer have usually been studied as single factors. Professor Arto Mannermaa intends to explore the big picture and look for more factors which significantly increase the risk of illness when they interact. This is where artificial intelligence comes in.

Mannermaa's team is developing algorithms that can learn on the basis of genomic and clinical data, and identify and predict risk factors. Learning algorithms are also used in the interpretation of mammography images. Genomic and clinical data are integrated to an AI model that not only helps to determine the risk of illness, but also in drawing up individual treatment plans.

"I'm a biologist and geneticist by training. I engaged in the close study of human

genetics and specialised as a hospital geneticist. I have been working on clinical studies in genetics laboratories, but have been interested in cancer throughout my researcher career," says Arto Mannermaa.

Mannermaa is a Professor of personalised medicine and biobanking at the University of Eastern Finland. In his research, he has focused on the genetics of breast and ovarian cancer. Since its inception, Mannermaa's team has been involved in the work of the world's larg-

est genetic epidemiology consortium, the Breast Cancer Association Consortium (BCAC). The consortium has the world's largest centralised collection of breast cancer tissue samples, collected from over 200,000 patients and controls. The collection includes well-annotated data on factors and clinical results related to breast cancer.

"My research team has been engaged in long-term work to determine the genetic risk variants of breast cancer. We can

Risk factors for breast cancer include the total amount of oestrogen during a lifetime and weight. Other risk factors are smoking, alcohol consumption and exercise.

now identify some 200 variants within normal genomic variation which increase the risk of getting breast cancer. Together with the BCAC, we have also learned about the genetic mutations that are major contributing factors to breast cancer. These include among others mutations of the BRCA and PALB-2 gene, which we were involved in finding to be a contributing factor in breast cancer.”

If a woman has a BRCA1 or BRCA2 gene mutation, she has a 60–80% risk of developing breast cancer. The risk impact of PALB-2 is almost the same.

Huge amounts of data

It is estimated that genome accounts for about 30 per cent of susceptibility to breast cancer, while 70 per cent is determined by environmental factors. Risk factors for breast cancer include the total amount of oestrogen during a lifetime, which depends on the number of pregnancies and children, and weight. Other factors include smoking, alcohol consumption and exercise. According to Mannermaa, risk factors tend to have been studied one at a time. Now the BCAC has been able to study the prevalence of breast cancer in the close relatives of patients. This includes plenty of international material that can be used for making comparisons.

”For example, studies have been done on whether there are more common factors in Finnish cancer data than in international data.”

Research material has been obtained from the Biobank of Eastern Finland and Kuopio University Hospital.

”The research team is grateful to all volunteers who participated in the study. Without their consent, this kind of work would not be possible.”

Finnish data has been compared with data obtained through BCAC, collected from more than 100 research teams around the world.

”Finns form a uniquely isolated population. In Finland there has identified many diseases linked to the Finnish disease genome, and genetic changes related to these. But the situation with multifactorial diseases, such as breast cancer, is surely the same, meaning that some risk factors are related to our population. Some of the genetic risk factors

for multifactorial diseases only occur in Finns.”

Although data has been obtained from around the world, for Mannermaa the challenge lies in the fact that the material was collected for different purposes, and is not always in the same format.

”In order to use the material, the data collected from different sources must be unified, which often takes up a large amount of the total time spent on research.”

Aiming for the big picture in breast cancer risk factors

The question Mannermaa wants to answer is which factors have contributed to the onset of breast cancer in a patient. Mannermaa’s team has created an AI model for breast cancer risk factors that is being tested with Finnish and international material.

”We also have material obtained from the Biobank. We are comparing the data of breast cancer patients and healthy individuals and trying to find the interactive combination of all variables that has the greatest influence on the onset of breast cancer.”

One of the study’s targets concerns normal genomic variation, or SNPs. The rapid development of DNA sequencing techniques has made it possible to determine single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), providing a very accurate estimate of the differences between individuals. SNP is the difference in the DNA

chain caused by a mutation within a population. According to some estimates, the human genome has 4–5 million SNPs, located in the DNA chain, either in the intergene or gene region. They can act as biomarkers, helping researchers to locate genes related to diseases. Certain SNPs can affect the operation of the gene and thus directly affect the onset of the disease.

“In practice, we focus on the differences between cancer patients and control groups. We want to learn how many SNPs are in common with these groups, and what the common SNP network is like among cancer patients compared to healthy individuals.”

Mannermaa’s team is working to identify SNPs related to breast cancer, by means of AI and learning algorithms.

“We teach our algorithm to detect SNP networks. With the help of artificial intelligence, we can identify the interactive group of SNPs with the greatest impact on disease risk.”

The results have been promising. The algorithm helped to identify genes close to SNPs, and these SNPs are probably affecting the operation of the genes. We found a gene network related to oestrogen metabolism.

“Oestrogen metabolism is a key component in the development of breast cancer, while another group that we found was related to apoptosis, or programmed cell death. Apoptosis is crucial in cancer development, because cancer cells must be able to prevent programmed cell death. That’s why we believe that the AI models helped us find the correct breast cancer factors.”

Supercomputing required

The amount of data in Mannermaa’s team’s study is so huge that CSC’s supercomputing capacity is required.

“About 200,000 SNPs can be identified from one laboratory sample. Each SNP is compared with all the others. In addition, we simulate genetic variation, in other words what SNPs they have in common but remain unidentified. This means that up to another 10 million SNPs can be added to the equation. Add to this variables from imaging and the biobank, and computing capacity is definitely called for.”

The basic model of the Mannermaa team’s AI is based on genetic data. Clinical variables, i.e. breast cancer risk factors, have now been added to this model. Mannermaa believes that the models will significantly improve diagnostics.

“Artificial intelligence enhances screening and diagnostics. In the future, we can avoid overdiagnosis and use the data to differentiate those who need more

accurate screening from those who don’t. This means that certain women do not need frequent mammography, due to their low risk of developing breast cancer.

Once genetic data is combined with not only known risk factors but also breast cancer diagnosis and treatment, the predictability of the disease will improve and personalised treatment plans can be drawn up.

Biobanks play a crucial role in research of this type. It is essential that all data is available.

“If the person giving a sample has consented to their data being used for biobank purposes, this data is combined with other data. The Biobank Act in Finland is the basis for secure data storage, and enables people who have given their consent to cancel it if they wish. Biobank consent is general consent based on the law. Through biobanks, everyone has the opportunity to participate in research aimed at developing health care.”

According to Mannermaa, the health data can be used to evaluate the impact of the research results. In addition to receiving plenty of data on the actual patient, we can see the impact of cancer patients’ treatment alternatives and solutions based on new research.

“The model and its prediction can help determine how it affects a patient’s life, and how resources should be allocated. This can make treatment more effective in the future. Patient-specific profiling and individualised treatments help to provide the right treatments for the right patients, and thereby make health care more efficient. This requires a multidisciplinary network.”

“In the future, we can avoid overdiagnosis and use the data to differentiate those who need more accurate screening from those who don’t.”

Tissue samples into digital images, interpreted by artificial intelligence

Turku University Hospital and Auria Biobank aim to have all tissue specimens in digital format. The samples would be scanned from glass slides, with diagnostics in pathology performed on computers. They will also develop artificial intelligence models, or classifiers, to identify e.g. cancer from digitalised samples.

Turku University Hospital alone takes 200,000 patient samples every year. Tissue samples are placed in formalin and cast into a paraffin block that can be sliced and subsequently examined under a microscope. The paraffin blocks are stored at the end of the process. Managing the samples is laborious and time-consuming. Systematic digitalisation of the samples makes the job easier.

"Since the samples are so numerous, metadata will enable us to quickly find the samples that we want," says **Antti Karlsson**, data analyst at Auria Biobank.

You can, for example, search the database for all samples indicating breast cancer tumours. By using metadata, searches can be narrowed down to pinpoint, say, samples with a certain receptor status from 60-year-old breast cancer patients.

In the digital pathology project, samples on microscope slides are scanned. Then a pathologist can view the samples on a computer screen and describe and classify them. All this annotation data is relevant to teaching artificial intelligence to automatically detect abnormalities

such as cancer cells in the samples. This would considerably speed up the work of pathologists. Auria Biobank has invested in data analytics, development of algorithms, and machine learning models.

Language model in support of metadata description

Turku University Hospital has huge numbers of tissue specimens stored on microscope slides. The problem is that no metadata can be stored on the slides and transferred into databases automatical-

duce different kinds of data that should be presented in a systematic way.

Artificial intelligence model identifies cancer automatically from samples

Metadata and digitalised sample material are used to develop artificial intelligence applications, for example, which are taught to automatically classify the locations with cancer cells in images. To teach the artificial intelligence system, we require some material classified by pathologists. According to Antti Karlsson, you do not in fact need very many images for the algorithm to start learning.

"A few dozen images is enough to get started. A single, whole slice image may yield a thousand small images that can be used to train the models."

This means that up to 10,000 small images can be obtained from 20 patients.

"A large image cannot be used with an algorithm, because no computer has the kind of graphics processor memory required to deal with it."

Karlsson stresses that artificial intelligence models which examine images are different to models examining texts.

"There is growing interest in how digitalised cancer tissue samples can be used to identify various issues."

"Clearly, they are all manifestations of artificial intelligence, and even of neural networks, but their structures and operating principles are quite different. Artificial intelligence is actually more like a collection of tools, each one of which is useful for a specific application."

Auria Biobank's Director **Lila Kallio** says that, in addition to genome data being used for research purposes, digital pathology making use of data analytics is a focus area at Auria.

"There is growing interest in how digitalised cancer tissue samples can be used to identify various issues. We are involved in studies where we try to use an algorithm to examine an image of a primary cancer tumour and predict how it will respond to treatment, or whether the primary cancer tumour will metastasise.

ly. The idea now is that pathologists add metadata to new samples by means of graphics software.

Karlsson says that the work is mechanical to begin with. Pathologists use graphics software to indicate the points where e.g. cancer is found on the scanned samples.

Description data is also required. This is where neural-network language models might come in. A pathologist would add information about the sample directly into a computer. This has been studied in cooperation with **Filip Ginter's** research team at the Department of Future Technologies of the University of Turku. The research team has focused on how computer software can be used to analyse natural text and speech. From a large amount of unclassified text, the language model learns how a spoken language seems to work statistically. Auria Biobank and Turku University Hospital are interested in how medical statement texts could be formed into classified and structural information by means of language models.

"One application of digital pathology could be to mine various types of information from statements, such as which part of the sample contains interesting tissue, making sample selection for research purposes easier. We could also develop a model that automatically structures regular medical statement texts. Pathologists could speak in 'prose', which artificial intelligence would collect and compile into a structured table."

According to Karlsson, such tables are already used relatively frequently, for example when pathologists have agreed on what aspects of each tumour should be reported.

"At the moment we are experimenting with these models, for example to detect and classify smoking data from among hundreds of thousands of statements, and to detect cancer metastases, symptoms related to hospital infections and various diagnoses."

The challenge is that data comes in a variety of forms. For example, scanners by different equipment manufacturers pro-

The most common staining method when determining basic structures of tissues is hematoxylin-eosin staining that can be used to stain various structures in tissues on the basis of their pH. Alkaline hematoxyline stains the acidic nuclei of cells violet, while acidic eosin stains the alkaline support structures of the cell – such as the connective and muscle tissue – red. The image shows HE-stained tissue, with the potentially interesting structure indicated. The pathologist draws an area in the image and names it appropriately. By creating enough examples like this, we can train artificial intelligence models to create similar descriptions and classifications automatically.

There are indications that the algorithm may be able to predict something that is not otherwise visible from a histological image.”

One-stop service

According to Lila Kallio, Finland has been a pioneering country in data management and sharing. The Finnish Biobank Act has enabled research and the combination of data from various registers. It is critically important that clinical information can be connected to samples.

”Services for researchers have been provided on a one-stop basis. Biobanks take care of the permits, collect the samples and combine all clinical data related to the research. All this can then be combined with other data, such as genetic data.”

Researchers get all the samples through a biobank.

”Biobanks cooperate in Finland. Researchers can request samples from all Finnish biobanks with a single request

made to the Finnish Biobank Cooperative.

According to Lila Kallio, the challenge now and in the future is data storage and management.

”Data is stored inside firewalls in hospital districts. If diagnostic samples will be digitalised on a larger scale within pa-

thology, the storage capacity problem must be solved as well. In addition, the image sizes are so huge that they cannot be transferred on ordinary data networks.

CSC plays an important role in terms of computing power, and safe storage and usage environments.

Big Picture: European storage place for digital pathology data is being planned.

Efficient processing and sharing of data improving disease diagnosis and treatment

Next-generation analysis methods of genes and RNA molecules enable faster and easier analyses. Data can also be stored well and shared with research teams through the Allas user interface of the CSC.

Next-generation sequencing (NGS) methods are used to study variations in the human genome and changes in genetic expression. The analysis of billions of sequence fragments provided by the NGS methods can be performed in a single computer run.

The new methods enable us to study numerous genes and targets from different samples simultaneously. This means that we can quickly analyse individual cells, such as cancer cells. We can also analyse cell-free DNA from blood plasma, indicating quickly and reliably whether the selected treatments have been effective and specifically whether any metastases remain.

Platforms used by the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM) and CSC use a range of algorithms to analyse data produced

“One of the most important ones is Broad Institute’s Genome Analysis Toolkit (GATK).”

by sequencing methods (exomes, genomes and transcriptomes). One of the most important ones is Broad Institute’s Genome Analysis Toolkit (GATK). This is used to look for gene variants and identify changes in the DNA or RNA sequence in the cell line. GATK analysis software has become the de facto bioinformat-

ics standard in the scientific community. GATK software can also be run on the superfast Dynamic Read Analysis for GENomics (Dragen) platform. CSC maintains Dragen, in collaboration with FIMM. Dragen performs the computing-intensive primary analysis of the sequence data, which is followed by the downstream bioinformatics analysis by the researchers. This makes the CSC storage capacity beneficial, because analysed data will not fit into any conventional computer, instead it is shared directly to users through the Allas service.

Cooperation between CSC and FIMM is crucial in terms of completing the analyses quickly.

“When we have at our disposal high-capacity sequencing platforms, algorithms and computing power, we get quick results. Today we can analyse one genome in a single day, as opposed to several weeks using older systems,” says **Pekka Ellonen**.

Mr Ellonen is Head of Laboratory at the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM). The unit uses modern methods to provide the research community genomics (DNA) and transcriptomics (RNA) analyses. The unit receives samples from various research projects.

“We agree with the researchers on the most suitable methods and customise the optimal toolkit to test their hypothesis. Such methods may include exome sequencing, genome sequencing, the sequencing of various RNA molecules (transcriptome), and genetic expression,” says Ellonen.

These methods are able to determine a tissue sample’s genes (genomics) or identify all genes (transcriptomics) and

proteins (proteomics) present in the tissue. The sequencing of the exome, that is, the regions that code the proteins can help in the study of hereditary diseases, congenital developmental disorders and cancer. Genetic expression is regulated accurately in cells and any changes may lead to illness. The research can focus on, for example, the differences between cancerous and healthy tissue.

Analytics of a single cell

Next-generation sequencing methods enable the study of complex biological systems. According to Ellonen, by far the greatest development in bioinformatics in recent years has been the analysis of single cells. Single cells are analysed in collaboration by the Single-Cell Analytics (SCA) unit of the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland and the sequencing unit.

Each cell contains the individual’s every gene, but certain genes are only expressed in certain cells and often only under certain conditions. Genetic expression and protein production in cells varies at different stages of development and as

a result of illnesses. This causes changes in the cellular and tissue functions. The analytics of a single cell does not actually refer to a single cell.

“Now we are able to study, for example, cancer cells as individual targets. We cannot reach a reliable result merely by determining the base sequence or genetic expression in a single cell; we must study samples of thousands or tens of thousands of cells,” says Ellonen.

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) can reveal regular inter-gene interaction, cell lineages and differences and the cell’s framework in its environment.

Single-cell sequencing also shows various and even new types of cell and genetic expression data about the functioning. Single-cell DNA sequencing, on the other hand, provides information about mutations taking place in small cell populations among normal cells. Single-cell accuracy provides information on the genetic differences of tumours, which is helpful in their treatment.

“The number of living cells in the sample being studied is verified in the laboratory, after which each cell is separated into its own droplet, enabling single-cell DNA or RNA molecules to be marked with molecule- and cell-specific DNA barcodes. The molecule-specific, cell-specific and eventually the sample-specific DNA barcodes enable both the identification of molecules in each cell and a financially efficient sequencing,” says **Pirkko Mattila**, head of the Single-Cell Analytics (SCA) unit of the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland.

“One sequencing run will profile thousands of cells at a time from multiple samples. This results in, from the analysis of thousands or up to hundreds of thousands of cells, a single-cell resolution, enabling us to study the properties of a single cell.”

Liquid biopsy

Liquid biopsy refers to taking a liquid sample, containing cells or parts of cells, from living tissue, such as blood. Liquid biopsy is a promising monitoring tool for cancer treatment without invasive surgical operations.

“We create sequencing libraries from genomic regions interesting from the viewpoint of various cancers,” says Pekka Ellonen.

Liquid biopsy can also be used for identifying cancer in its early stages. A

Cell-free DNA (cfDNA) refers to DNA circulating in the blood stream outside the blood cells. CfDNA fragments enter the blood circulation either due to apoptosis or necrosis. Normally, these fragments are cleaned up by macrophages, but the overproduction of cells in cancer causes cfDNA in the blood stream. Cell-free DNA ends up to the bloodstream also in healthy cells. A part of the cell-free DNA in the cancer patients originates from the tumor. This circulating cfDNA and especially the fraction originated from tumor (circulating tumor DNA, ctDNA) is a promising research subject for the projects with the goal of individual cancer treatments. In addition to blood samples cell-free DNA can be analysed in urine, spinal fluid and saliva samples. The Sequencing Unit of the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM) is looking for remnants of such DNA by means of sequencing.

High throughput sequencing equipment produces 1–20 billion sequence fragments, depending on the type of run. The NovaSeq6000 can have four runs of different capacity. The lowest-capacity run can sequence a couple of dozen exomes. The exome is composed of all of the exons within the genome, corresponding to about one per cent of the entire genome. The highest-capacity run can analyse 24 genomes at a time. Whole genome sequencing (WGS) covers the entire genome, 3.1 billion bases. Some 1.2 billion short sequences are created to analyse a single human genome, which are combined with algorithms to create the genome being analysed. In order to obtain a reliable answer, the base pairs are read several times (reading depth). When looking for changes typical for cancer, for example, the reading depth may be 500–1000. This means that the analysis may focus on an exome, for example.

blood sample provides information on tumour blood cells or DNA fragments they have secreted into the blood-stream.

“Tumours are usually in a difficult place, requiring a surgical procedure to remove them or take a sample of them. When tumours grow uncontrollably, there is a higher than normal amount of cell deaths. Dying cancer cells release DNA fragments into the bloodstream. These DNA fragments are collected for sequencing from a blood sample’s cell-free fraction, plasma and serum. Analysis of the sequencing results can show whether the bloodstream contains DNA fragments containing changes typical of cancers,” says Ellonen.

Ellonen says that liquid biopsy is used extensively and it is related to many new research projects. Liquid biopsy can be used not only in basic research but also

**“Data processing
can be performed
using standard
programming interfaces
from anywhere.”**

to make a treatment plan and to monitor treatment effects or cancer recurrence. Being able to take many blood samples at different times will help doctors understand what kind of molecule changes have taken place in the body.

“New genetic markers may be identified and, in the best-case scenario, an accurate treatment method can be selected on the basis of the observed mutations. Alternatively, you may know what you are looking for, that is, you are monitoring for

residual signs of the disease in the body, in other words whether the surgical procedure removed the cancer completely.”

Pekka Ellonen is enthusiastic about Allas storage service’s user interface, enabling laboratories and research institutions to share pre-processed sequencing results and molecular data with researchers, research teams and consortia. Allas provides 12 petabytes of storage space for sensitive genetic data. The data is securely available through the Web. Data processing can be performed using standard programming interfaces from anywhere.

“Public money produces data, which should be shared in time with the wider scientific community, obviously appropriately pseudonymised. The user interface enables the sharing of large materials, such as the cohort material of useful genomic data.”

Teaching an algorithm to identify cancer from sequence data

Deep learning has revolutionised cancer research. Deep neural networks can automatically detect features within a patient's sample data that can be used to identify cancers. In the future, learning algorithms will be able to identify potential early-stage cancers from a blood sample. Esa Pitkänen and his research group at the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM) are developing a new generation of deep-learning algorithms.

Algorithms have been used to identify cells in sectional images of tissue samples. For instance, if tissue cells appear atypical, the algorithm will spot this and determine if the cells are cancerous. DNA sequence data from tumours is now being used along with imaging data to identify cancers.

“Until recently, it was difficult to tell from a DNA sequence what kind of tumour an identified sequence came from. Now new technologies and deep learning algorithms have been created,” Pitkänen says.

Pitkänen and his team are developing algorithms that identify short, repetitive

snippets of DNA sequences. These algorithms can be used to find DNA sequences that mutate frequently in a particular type of cancer or to which certain proteins involved in gene regulation bind. Analysis of these sequences can be used for various purposes, such as charting the causes of cancer and developing medicines.

“The replication of DNA in cell division is not perfect; mutations can occur during the process. The division of a single cell involves the copying of about six billion nucleotide pairs in DNA, so errors will inevitably occur. Even the slightest probability of errors is enough to guarantee mutations,” says Pitkänen.

“If enough mutations occur in genes that prevent tumour growth, for example, cancer may start to develop.”

An example of this is a point mutation in which one base within the DNA strand is replaced with another. The enzymes involved in copying DNA may make a mistake when a cell is dividing, for instance by incorrectly repairing the part of DNA that was damaged by ultraviolet radiation from sunlight. A typical mutation caused by ultraviolet radiation that can result in skin cancer is that two consecutive cytosine (C) base molecules in the base pairs

of human DNA are converted to two thymine (T) base molecules. When skin cancer-specific mutations of this type are detected in sufficient numbers, the algorithms can learn to associate them with a particular type of cancer.

“We try to predict the type of cancer and tumour from the mutations. This also provides information on how treatment can be developed.”

Identifying cancer from blood sample DNA using algorithms

Pitkänen and his group analyse blocks of sequences and train algorithms to pinpoint deviations in them. From these abnormalities, the algorithm can detect tumours and classify them into different cancer types.

“Before joining the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland, I worked at the European Molecular Biology Laboratory in Heidelberg, where I participated in the

Pan-Cancer Analysis of Whole Genomes (PCAWG) project. This project involved the analysis of more than 2,600 entire cancer genomes. My group is using data from the PCAWG project in several of our cancer genomics projects.”

“We try to predict the type of cancer and tumour from the mutations.”

An algorithm developed by the group has been taught the mutations found in the tumour samples of 2,600 cancer patients. This sample set contained about 47 million mutations. Approximately 50 million somatic mutations were found in the sequence data.

“We trained the algorithm to try to deduce the type of cancer from these sequence changes. Once the algorithm is given all the mutations of different tumours and their sequences, in the future it will be able to determine the kind of tumour that has been detected. This de-

“A researcher in my group, **Prima Sanjaya**, has developed neural network models for analysing sequence data. Every now and then, researchers come across cases in which a cancer has metastasised without being able to tell where it has spread from. Such cases could in the future be dealt with by means of a liquid biopsy – that is, it will hopefully be possible to determine from a blood sample if the patient has cancer, and if so, what kind.”

Liquid biopsies are based on the fact that cells release into the bloodstream and other body fluids a type of DNA called cell-free DNA (cfDNA). Cancer cells also release DNA, which makes it possible to test for cancer mutations in the blood plasma.

“If a liquid biopsy shows traces of cancer, we don’t know exactly what kind of cancer it is, as it could have entered the bloodstream from anywhere in the body. If we have the means to examine these cases more closely, for example with deep learning algorithms, we could

obtain valuable information on where in the patient’s body the tests should be focused. The algorithm may indicate that the source of the cancer DNA could be the large intestine, for example. I believe that such algorithms will become extremely important. Liquid biopsy and algorithms can make it possible to diagnose cancers without surgery.”

Identifying intestinal cancers using algorithms

In addition to hereditary factors, the development of cancer also depends on the person’s lifestyle. Plentiful research has been conducted at the University of Helsinki on various cancers, such as intestinal cancers.

“It is known that eating red meat contributes to the incidence of colorectal cancer. The mechanisms by which the disease is caused require further research, but in recent years a lot of progress has been made in understanding the significance of DNA alkylation reactions, which are caused by red meat, for example.”

Colorectal cancer is one of the most dangerous cancers in Western countries. In countries such as Finland, it leads to death in 30 per cent of cases. About 15 per cent of colorectal cancers belong to the cancer group that exhibits microsatellite instability (MSI). Microsatellites are sequences of DNA that can vary in length from person to person, and thus function as individual identifiers in much the same way as fingerprints. Microsatellite instability occurs when the post-replication repair mechanism of cellular DNA does not function properly. This causes mutations to begin to accumulate, especially in microsatellites.

“In an MSI tumour, microsatellites are easily vulnerable to single-base additions or deletions. For example, out of eight consecutive adenine microsatellites, one adenine may be lost. When it occurs in a gene, such a change causes a complete transformation in the content of the amino acid chain of the protein that is encoded by the gene. If there are enough changes in genes that are important for preventing uncontrolled cell growth, cancer may begin to develop.”

MSI is often associated with other cancers as well as colorectal cancer, such as stomach, uterine, ovarian and brain cancer. MSI analysis can be used in the

“Liquid biopsies are based on the fact that cells release into the bloodstream and other body fluids a type of DNA called cell-free DNA.”

duction process is based on the algorithm learning these connections.”

Through deviations in the sequence data in tumours, the algorithm learns to identify when a given tumour corresponds to a particular type of cancer. It can group tumours based on sequence data alone.

See also Jiao et al. Nature Communications 2020

In their work, Esa Pitkänen and his research team used one of the world’s largest data sets, from the Pan-Cancer Analysis of Whole Genomes (PCAWG) project. It contains 47 million mutations. The data is from sequenced tumour samples from 2,600 patients. The collection included 37 tumour types from different cancers, including colorectal cancer, lung cancer and melanomas. Prima Sanjaya used deep neural networks to create a machine learning model that processes the sequencing data of each patient and presents this data in two-dimensional map format. In this image, each point represents one distinct tumour obtained from a patient. The different colours represent the different types of tumours. Interestingly, the model groups colorectal cancers together, but also distinguishes three subtypes (marked with arrows in the figure).

1. External factors (e.g. UV radiation from sunlight), 2. Internal factors (e.g. a spontaneous deamination reaction, in which the amine group of a base changes, for example from adenine to uracil) 3. DNA copying errors.

A mutation is a change in the nucleotide sequence of DNA or RNA. A nucleotide consists of a base, a sugar molecule and a phosphate group. The sugar in DNA is deoxyribose and the sugar in RNA is ribose. The four nitrogenous bases that DNA contains are guanine (G), adenine (A), cytosine (C) and thymine (T). RNA has three of the same bases as DNA, but instead of thymine its fourth base is uracil (U).

A mutation may be a change of a single nucleotide – that is, a point mutation – or the change may involve multiple

nucleotides. In a point mutation, one base is replaced by another in the RNA or DNA strand. Large mutations can involve thousands of nucleotides, and are called structural changes. A structural change can affect multiple genes at the same time. Cancers are usually caused by several somatic mutations. Mutations of this kind are not inherited, and can occur at any time of life from embryonic development onwards. Mutations may bring about a change in the functioning of a normal cell, causing it to begin to divide uncontrollably.

At the middle of the picture are presented different types of mutations, distribution of mutations on chromosomes and epigenetic information. Epigenetic inheritance is influenced by many external factors, such as nutrition. An

example is the development of identical twins so as to become distinct from each other in appearance.

- Modelling mutations:
- Linear models
- Deep neural networks
- Transformer models.

Transformers are a family of deep learning models that work particularly well with certain types of data, such as textual data. This makes them well suited to machine translation, for instance. In cancer research, transformer models can draw attention to mutation types that are important for identifying a particular type of cancer. For example, in skin cancers that contain many sunlight-induced mutations (C> T, CC> TT), the transformer will focus on these particular mutations.

prognosis of cancer. The treatment choice may be influenced by the analysis.

“An interesting thing is that the deep neural network is also learning to classify different subtypes of cancers. For instance, it identified the MSI subtype of colorectal cancers,” says Pitkänen.

CSC is one of the main partners in the Personalised Medicine in Europe (PerMedCoE) project. For example, the three-year the HPC/Exascale Centre of Excellence for Personalised Medicine in Europe project is aimed at making effective use of cancer-related data in

healthcare and speeding up the process of diagnosis.

“Individualised treatments of the future, among them cancer treatments, will be based on a precise understanding of the patient and their illness. This will result from gathering a large volume of data of different types, such as tumour-related data and imaging data during cancer treatment. Many data collection methods produce a mass of data, and the new computational methods developed for analysing it require a very large amount of computational resources,” says Pitkänen.

“Developing a new computational method from the idea stage into a functional healthcare technology is a huge challenge in an operating environment like this. With cancer treatments in particular, it is important that information relevant to patient care be made available to the doctors as rapidly as possible. I’m confident that the results of the PerMed CoE project will provide a basis for deriving relevant information from a colossal volume of health data to help doctors in their work, and thus significantly improve treatment outcomes.”

Finnish research team sequences the genomes of thousands of individuals with diabetes to look for genetic risk factors

Diabetes is a major chronic disease that comes with a number of associated conditions that pose remarkable challenges. Such diseases include diabetic kidney disease, diabetic retinopathy, coronary heart disease and strokes. Now, a Finnish research team sequences the genomes of thousands of individuals with diabetes to look for genetic risk factors.

Individuals with diabetes have a higher risk of cardiac diseases in comparison to the rest of the population. A third of individuals with type 1 diabetes, earlier also called juvenile diabetes, develop kidney disease that has a remarkable impact on mortality and the risk of cardiac disease. On the other hand, diabetic retinopathy is the most significant cause of blindness among working-age population.

Finnish children and young adults have the highest risk of type 1 diabetes in the world. Type 2 diabetes is often considered a disease of the western life style, but the highest patient concentrations are found in middle-income countries with China and India topping the statistics of individual countries.

“Diabetes is associated with remarkable and severe complications.

The associated conditions have a major impact on the quality of life and life expectancy,” explains **Niina Sandholm**, Genetic Epidemiologist at Folkhälsan Research Centre. Sandholm is involved in the FinnDiane research project, the objective of which is to identify hereditary and environmental risk factors predisposing to diabetic complications. FinnDiane-study is a collaboration project

between University of Helsinki, Helsinki University Hospital (HUS) and Folkhälsan Research Center.

According to Sandholm, genetic data could be beneficial to young patients in particular, already at an early stage prior to the emergence of risk factors.

“Currently, the use of genetic data in clinical treatment is mostly associated with rare diseases, but our results and earlier research suggest that extensive genetic data could also be utilised in the early prevention of common diseases.”

One of the largest research projects on diabetes

FinnDiane, established by Professor Per-Henrik Groop in 1997, is a follow-up study participated in by almost 8,000 individuals with type 1 diabetes. The participants are recruited at 80 hospitals and health centres across Finland. It is one of the most extensive research materials on type 1 diabetes and associated complications in the world. Now, this material is used for sequencing the genome of over 1,800 patients.

Sandholm has experience in research projects where genome-wide association study (GWAS) is applied as research method. The method is particularly useful when the genetic background of the studied disease is complex. It enables identifying genetic variants that either increase the risk of diabetes or protect from the disease. The GWAS method involves identifying genetic variants from the participants’ blood samples. The number of these variants ranges from hundreds of thousands to millions, and the number of patients may vary between thousands and hundreds of thousands.

A GWAS study on 5,600 FinnDiane participants with type 1 diabetes revealed, for example, a new genetic locus related to cardiac diseases close to the DEFB127 gene. It is the most extensive study of its kind to date. Locus means the location of a DNA sequence on a chromosome. The variation of a sequence is called an allele.

The same study that identified the DEFB127 gene also revealed other genetic factors predisposing to cardiac diseases.

“Many predisposing genetic factors have been identified for cardiac diseases and other common medical conditions.

GWAS-SEQUENCING

WHOLE GENOME SEQUENCING

Whole genome sequencing of 1880 individuals with type 1 diabetes. Short sequence reads of 150 DNA bases. Average 30x coverage for each base. Since a human being has 3 billion bases, this means 600 million reads per person. Reading one genome takes one day per person.

400 million individuals in the world have diabetes. Half of them have diabetic complications. 35% have a genetic risk for the diabetic kidney disease (nephropathy). Other complications are eye diseases (glaucoma, retinopathy), diabetic foot, neuropathy, stroke, heart attack, and peripheral artery disease.

One of the most significant factors lies within the region of genes CDKN2A and CDKN2B. Diabetics have a remarkably higher risk of cardiac disease than the rest of the population, and there is little knowledge of the related genetic factors. Our research indicated that the same genetic area CDKN2A/B affects the risk of cardiac disease also in individuals with type one diabetes.”

A third of individuals with type 1 diabetes develop a kidney disease. Some may develop renal failure that may, at worst, lead to the need for dialysis treatment or a kidney transplant.

Another study analysed various data sources to identify connections to kidney disease in 27,000 diabetics. GWAS is a fast and economic method, but it cannot identify all variants. Therefore, the research team have turned to sequencing the entire genomes of patients.

“Variants identified with the GWAS method are common, and individual variants’ impact on the risk of developing a condition is quite moderate.

The objective of sequencing is to identify rare variants that may have a

“Many predisposing genetic factors have been identified for cardiac diseases and other common medical conditions.”

significant impact on developing a condition at the level of individual patients. The worst case scenario is that such a variant prevents the functioning of an entire protein.”

New variants identified from an enormous amount of data

According to Sandholm, the research results may help predict the risk of developing a condition or lead the way in developing new medicines.

“The broader goal of genetic research is to identify variants that affect the risk of developing a disease or directly cause

a disease. This enables a better understanding of the causes of diabetic complications.”

The ultimate goal is to learn to prevent and find cures to diseases associated with diabetes.

“Our aim is to read the entire DNA sequence of all patients. This will result in a huge amount of data,” says Sandholm.

“The sequencer produces DNA data in strands of 150 base pairs. To verify the data, our goal is to read each one of the three billion DNA base pairs an average of 30 times. This means that there will be 600,000 strands of 150 base pairs per patient.”

To map the entire sequence, the sequenced strands must be placed in the correct order with the help of a reference human genome. This requires enormous computing capacity which is provided by CSC.

“The purpose is to organise the data so that it would enable identifying how each base pair variant affects a given disease at the level of individual patients. Our aim is to identify rare variants that cannot be identified with the

GWAS method. Only a few patients in the sample exhibit rare variants.”

Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP), or variants in the DNA base pairs, are a sort of end result of the data processing.

“The variation in the DNA sequence is expressed as SNPs. Each patient has either no alleles or one or two variants. They are markers that indicate which diseases the variant may cause.”

The research group has already sequenced the entire genomes of 600 patients.

“Based on the initial results, we identified individual variants that are clearly associated with the risk of stroke, for example. There are also variants in genes that have previously been associated with congenital kidney diseases. Now it appears that variants in the same genes also affect the development of diabetic kidney disease.”

Along with her colleagues, Niina Sandholm studies the protein-coding parts of the gene and gene regulatory regions that may have links to risk factors contributing to diabetes.

“The area between genes – 95% of the genome – contains plenty of regulatory regions that determine which gene appears in which tissue. As such, the DNA sequence is the same in each human cell, but gene regulation causes

“ELIXIR, for one, invests in the development of full genome sequencing and genomic data processing methods.”

eyes to develop into eyes and kidneys into kidneys. In this respect, gene regulatory regions and their changes play a key role.”

Genome sequencing on an exceptional scale

This study is one of the world’s first to sequence the entire genome this extensively with regard to a specific disease. For the

time being, the sequencing of the entire genome is relatively rare.

“The current trend is to sequence the exome with a focus on the protein-coding parts. However, it is only a matter of time that sequencing the entire genome becomes more common. ELIXIR, for one, invests in the development of full genome sequencing and genomic data processing methods.”

CSC provides the ePouta service for processing sensitive data. In the ePouta cloud service, virtual private servers operate on CSC’s computing platform under increased data security. The users receive dedicated cloud resources which are separated from CSC’s other computing environments. The FinnDiane research group uses the computing cluster of Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM) which is connected to CSC’s sensitive data computing platform via the ePouta light path. By scaling the computing resources, the light path enables faster processing of the project data.

In addition, the researchers have been allocated a remarkable amount of storage space to store the genomic data.

Combining biobank data with data registers enables research towards

THL Biobank contains a large amount of data on the health and lifestyles of the Finnish population, the collection of which began already in the 1960s. When this is combined with genetic data stored in the biobank and with national health registers, illness risk factors can be effectively identified and predicted.

“Data in the biobank can be used for practically any health research,” says research manager **Kaisa Silander**, who has contributed to the descriptions and classification of THL Biobank’s population cohorts.

“We have plenty of data from various population research studies and when

these are put together, researchers have an impressively large material at their disposal.”

Silander considers the material to be significant also by international standards.

“I think it is as valuable as UK Biobank or Estonia Biobank. When biobank data is

combined with health registers, we have health information about certain people over a period of 40 years. We know exactly, for example, which diseases a certain person has had.”

Silander has been working with cohort data for a long time. Projects funded

from health personalised treatment

by e.g. EU Health programmes built the infrastructure. After that she helped combine the metadata for research cohorts managed by the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) into a searchable database.

“We built a common infrastructure for data storage, because all these cohorts contain similar data. First we created a catalogue in which these cohorts were described in a uniform manner. We saved the variable metadata into the same database, in order to make them easy to

search and to find. The description of the variables was done in Finnish and English. The same protocol will also be used for future cohort description,” says Silander.

THL Biobank was established in 2014. The population cohorts collected by THL had two traditional lines of research. Between 1965 and 1980 population health examination surveys were carried out by driving around the country on buses modified into mobile clinics. The mobile clinic examined more than 50,000 Finns around the country. THL’s population co-

horts are composed of information provided by the participants of the health surveys, of a baseline clinical examination, and of a sample bank. Most of the samples have been turned into data. For some participants up to 40 years or more of health register follow-up can be obtained. The mobile clinic was followed up in 2000–2001 by the nationwide Health 2000 study and a further follow-up of the latter in 2011–2012. The mobile clinic research included pulmonary diseases, heart conditions, anaemia and iron

deficiency, diabetes, kidney and urinary tract conditions, thyroid conditions, calcium metabolism diseases and coronary artery disease. Later the range of diseases has been extended, and today biobank studies can be conducted on any disease.

The FINRISK study has collected information mainly about risk factors for cardiovascular diseases and diabetes, originally in eastern and central Finland. Later the study was expanded to cover several other areas in Finland, and the range of diseases studied was also increased. In 2017, these two lines of research were combined in the FinHealth study.

“The cohorts contain plenty of lifestyle data obtained with survey questionnaires,” says Silander.

The questionnaires include questions about smoking, alcohol use and diet, sleeping and exercise habits. The health checks have included height, weight, blood pressure and other measurable matters. Blood, stool and urine samples have also been taken.

“The samples are used to determine biomarker levels, such as lipids and inflammation (C-reactive protein, CRP). CRP is a protein produced by the liver, and its

concentration in the body increases rapidly during inflammation.”

Kaisa Silander hopes that in the future we would be able to obtain much more biomarker data describing changes in a person’s body that may give an indication of an illness.

“If you can combine health register, questionnaire and genome data, it certainly enables extensive research areas.”

“There are good methods for high throughput biomarker analysis. Currently we have at the biobank information about more than two hundred biomarkers, which were analyzed by NMR spectroscopy. However, there are laboratories that can produce thousands of biomarkers from a single serum sample.

This type of information, combined with the FINRISK material, for example, would be valuable. There are still suitable serum samples for many of the FINRISK participants.”

Genomic data of cohorts

Thanks to the FinnGen research project, THL Biobank may offer genetic data for other biobank studies.

The goal of the FinnGen project, started in autumn 2017, is to collect the genome data of half a million Finns. The project utilises samples collected by all Finnish biobanks. Genome data is combined with data available in national healthcare registers. This gives a better understanding on how diseases develop, and identify new treatments. Phenotypes used in FinnGen are age, gender, height, weight and smoking. Genome data created in the FinnGen project is returned twice a year to the biobanks.

“If you can combine health register, questionnaire and genome data, it certainly enables extensive research areas,” says postdoctoral researcher **Heidi Marjonen**. She works as a genome expert at THL Biobank, processing genomic data of all THL Biobank cohorts.

Researchers can buy a service from THL Biobank in which a personal polygenic risk score for a specific disease for a person in cohort under study is calculated. This means that the researcher does not have to request the 'raw' genetic data and learn to do the necessary calculations.

THL Biobank's sample collections contain genotype data of densely mapped single variants of DNA, and also data of whole genome sequence, and exome sequence data of the protein coding regions of DNA.

All exome and whole genome sequence data related to the FINRISK and Health 2000 were produced at Washington University and the Broad Institute / Massachusetts Institute of Technology, which are among the leading laboratories for genomic studies. The FINRISK cohort includes data of 10,000 exome sequences and 4000 whole genome sequences.

"Now it will be possible to create personalized treatment methods. When lifestyle data is combined with genetic data, better drug treatments can be developed," says Marjonen.

According to Marjonen, DNA samples can also be used to produce epigenetic data.

Epigenetic inheritance means the transfer of hereditary data to an offspring of a cell or organism without the data being coded into the DNA or RNA

sequence. Epigenetic factors are affected by many external factors, such as dietary habits.

Another interesting dataset is the microbiome, which is data about the microbes in the human intestine. Stool samples from the 2002 FINRISK cohort have been studied to determine the sequence data of all microbes. This data can be utilised to see how the microbiome affects human health.

Personal polygenic risk score

Heidi Marjonen took part in a study in which more than 3,000 persons were given information of their 10-year disease risk for the most common diseases in Finland. When genetic data is combined with clinical data, one can predict individual's disease susceptibility. The overall 10-year risk evaluation was based on the genetic data and other traditional risk factors, such as gender, age, body mass index, blood pressure and cholesterol levels. The genetic risk was calculated as a personal polygenic risk score, taking into account millions genetic variations.

This data was stored on the ePouta platform for sensitive data in CSC, which enables a secure transfer between the portal's user interface and the database.

"The genetic risk was calculated as a personal polygenic risk score, taking into account millions genetic variations."

The polygenic risk score, says Heidi Marjonen, is a major research trend. The risk score is a single value that reveals the genetic burden of a disease.

"Researchers receive information about the genome in a convenient way, which allows to study the effect of genome on a disease or other traits in an individual."

Studying the human microbiome is a key towards holistic understanding of our health

Together, microbes and their interactions with the host are called a microbiome. Microbiome composition is unique to each person. The microbiome helps the body's defence system fight infections, for instance. If the microbiome is disturbed, the body could be exposed to diseases such as diabetes.

Leo Lahti, Associate Professor of Data Science from the University of Turku, is developing the machine learning models with his research group and partners for screening microbial signatures from large-scale data collections.

“The microbiome is just one element in development of diseases, but it is an element that we haven’t been able to study as extensively before, because the effective data collection methods we have now have become available only very recently,” says Lahti.

Lahti’s research group has characterized microbes in different habitats and ecosystems together with experimental researchers.

“Scientists are starting to have a pretty good idea of what kinds of species and groups of bacteria can be found in different environments. We have learned quite a lot about their function, tasks, and role in metabolism and the chemical compounds they produce.”

All bacteria and single-celled archaea are microbes. Microbes also include algae,

protozoa, yeasts and moulds. According to Lahti, microbial research has advanced rapidly after the prices of sequencing technologies started coming down. The DNA of microbial samples is sequenced and the species of microbes in the sample can be identified if they have been characterized earlier.

“The sample can come from the environment, parts of the human body, or just about anywhere. We study bits of DNA and try to put the puzzle together. That way we can determine the bacterial

The DNA of microbial samples is sequenced and the species of microbes in the sample can be identified if they have been characterized earlier. The sample can come for example from the environment, or parts of the human body.

composition of the given sample. We can even trace completely new bacterial genomes and discover previously unknown species,” says Lahti.

Microbes of the human body predict disease

The most diverse microbial ecosystem in our bodies thrives in the gut. According to current knowledge, a typical adult carries around 1 to 2 kg of bacteria on average, which is slightly more than the amount of human cells. There are many levels in the human microbiome, and the levels form diverse ecosystems. The composition of a person’s microbiome is affected by their genome and living environment. Habits such as diet and an outdoorsy lifestyle have been shown to affect the composition of a person’s microbiome. A person’s microbes can be used to deduce whether the person is a vegetarian or an omnivore, for example. Lahti’s research group has also been involved in studying the microbial compositions of different population groups.

“Identifying the species in the human microbiome in general was a huge task. The composition can vary geographically, i.e. according to where people live and whether they belong to the indigenous population, or whether they live in the city or the countryside, or their standard of living.”

Studying the composition helps with understanding how microbes are connected to a person’s health.

“In this context, linking a person’s current state of health with their future health status takes centre stage. Is it possible to infer something on a person’s current or even future state of health by looking at their microbiome? And if it is possible, can the person’s health be affected by modifying the microbial composition, and what kinds of risks or ethical questions are related to this? Computational and machine learning techniques are in a key role in extracting information from the complex data sets that are now being generated.”

In Finland, stool samples were collected in connection with the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare’s (THL) FINRISK population survey in 2002. The many years’ worth of follow-up data from these individuals is now enabling the study of the links between microbiome composition and long-term changes in health status. Lahti says the extensive Finnish population cohort collected by THL is unique at a global level.

“The data is very valuable; carrying out a study like this would be hard in many countries because similar comprehensive population register data is often not available. We now have a huge number of samples and associated health infor-

mation that we can use to study the link between microbial composition and population health.”

According to Lahti, some microbial analyses can be used in diagnostics. They could be used to identify specific diseases or to identify microbes that predispose humans to the risk of certain cancers. For example, *Helicobacter pylori* found in the stomach may increase the risk of stomach cancer.

“Certain groups of bacteria are found in the gut that are statistically linked to the risk of developing a disease later on. We have recently discovered that they can indicate an increased risk of mortality, liver disease, and type 2 diabetes, for instance. We do not yet understand the causal relationships between these observations, but we can see the signals years before a person gets sick.”

Research results have been published on mortality rates, liver diseases, and type 2 diabetes.

“These are significant disease groups that are studied frequently anyway. Despite the long research traditions associated with them, microbiome studies have brought a new perspective into understanding these diseases. Microbes play a part in our metabolism. The compounds produced by microbes in the body can have a significant role in these diseases and in immune systems.”

“After we learn more about what these microbes do and what microbes are found in our bodies, we will have a better chance at understanding the mechanisms that affect the development of diseases. This can help with developing new ways to curb the effects of diseases or prevent the risk of developing them in the first place.”

According to Lahti, there is currently huge medical interest in microbiomes, because lifestyle changes and many common diseases have been found to be linked to changes in the microbial balance. In addition to this, antimicrobial resistance is a growing health problem, among others. It refers to the increased ability of bacteria to withstand antibiotics, and it is predicted to be the leading cause of death in the coming decades.

Machine learning models

Lahti’s research group extracts information from big data and merges information from different sources. The size of datasets is constantly increasing, and they need to be structured and organized in order to make them understandable. Such analyses have many computational steps. First, the data must be pre-processed and the DNA fragments must be combined in order to see which species they come from and in which proportions they oc-

cur in different samples. After this, the connections between the microbial composition and the living environment or state of health of the host organism can be studied in more detail.

“Data can be complicated. It can be hierarchical and have temporal or spatial structure. So, we need new computational methods. For example, machine learning methods are useful because they reduce the need for human intervention, which means we can automate a significant part of the processing and transfer it to machines.”

According to Lahti, methods that can assist people in making quantitative conclusions play a big part in biomedical research.

“Data is collected in databases. And when we analyse new samples, we want to combine the sample data with the data already in the databases. The newly observed data must be interpreted in the context of the previously collected data and accumulated knowledge.”

According to Lahti, when studying species of microbes, it is important to understand how they work together as an ecosystem and interact with the human body. Sequencing the genomes of groups of microbes and data integration can require massive computing and storage resources.

Photo: Agricultural Research Service, U.S Department of Agriculture

E. coli bacteria, magnified 10,000 times.

“We need the resources provided by CSC to obtain comprehensible information from the large-scale sequencing data that we can then analyse statistically. We increasingly use these services as a platform for cooperation. We can build workflows with other research groups and make the data available through CSC, and the data analysis platform is also in one place, on the CSC servers. It is also important that the bioinformatics data resources provided by ELIXIR can be accessed via CSC. We are also increasingly using these services to provide training in computational research methods.”

“There is currently huge medical interest in microbiomes, because lifestyle changes and many common diseases have been found to be linked to changes in the microbial balance.”

Better treatments for leukaemia

Professor Merja Heinäniemi and her research team at the University of Eastern Finland use computational methods to interpret cancer samples in order to determine which cellular processes are defective and how cells behave during drug treatments. The aim is to find effective medicinal treatments for leukaemia.

Leukaemia, or blood cancer, occurs when the precursors of white blood cells in the bone marrow turn into cancerous cells. Unlike other cancers, leukaemia is not a single tumour but instead consists of cancer cells

in the bloodstream and bone marrow. In children, leukaemia treatments are so effective that the prognosis for recovery is as high as 90 per cent. Heinäniemi points out that the disease may recur, however.

“Even if leukaemia is treatable after a relapse, it still means that chemotherapy, a long course of cytostatic drugs, takes several years. Therefore, more effective treatments are important, and for some

patients the treatments could be reduced. There are patients for whom it is difficult to find treatments, but on the other hand, treatments for childhood leukaemias last long.”

A professor of computational biomedicine, Heinäniemi studies how defects in gene regulations influence the development of cancer cells.

“Blood cancers include various types of leukaemias, acute and chronic leukaemias. Of these, myeloid leukaemias are mainly adult diseases, whereas lymphoblastic leukaemias are children’s diseases,” Heinäniemi explains.

In acute leukaemia, the blood stem cell genome in the bone marrow is altered and white blood cell precursors begin to divide uncontrollably. In children, the commonest form of leukaemia develops from a precursor of B- and T-cells of the immune defence system, and is called acute lymphoblastic leukaemia.

New drug candidates discovered through data analysis

Heinäniemi’s research group has carried out gene expression profiling analyses related to cancer. Gene expression refers to

a sequence of events in the cell in which the code in DNA is copied into RNA and then into a protein under the control of this messenger molecule. The gene that promotes cancer development can be activated or inactivated. Regulatory regions that affect gene function also play a role in the development of DNA damage in childhood leukaemia and more mature cancer of the lymphoid tissue.

In 2019, Heinäniemi and other researchers collected a large dataset of more than 10,000 patient samples. This data on haematological malignancies (HEMAP) will continue to be shared with

Leukaemia is caused by the transformation of precursor white blood cells in the bone marrow into malignant cancer cells. Leukaemia does not form a single tumour like other cancers – instead, the cancerous cells are found in the circulating blood and bone marrow. Leukaemia is a cancer of the bone marrow precursor cells. The image shows human blood cells and lymphocytes, one of the types of white blood cell. They are formed in the bone marrow. In leukaemia, the structure of the lymphocyte is altered and the proportion of diseased lymphocytes to white blood cells has increased.

researchers through CSC. They were able to deduce more than 30 types of cancer from this dataset by computational methods. In addition, new disease biomarkers and new drug candidates were discovered when the data was combined with drug target databases.

For example, subtypes of childhood leukaemia were found that behave differently at the molecular level.

“We can already see from the data clustering that even subtypes of the disease have unique genetic profiles and can be identified from the data. The combined data revealed to us, at the molecular level, the heterogeneity of the disease, and the similarities between different diseases.”

Heinäniemi has used the data to look for patients for whom treatment could be less rigorous. Cytostatic drugs are medicines used to destroy cancer cells. However, they can cause many side effects. Patients with a poor treatment

response also tend to have an increased risk of relapse.

Single-cell analysis helps find effective drug treatment

Together with **Olli Lohi** from Tampere University, Heinäniemi’s team mapped the entire human genome to see how different genes could act as predictors of childhood leukaemia.

“Potential biomarker genes for childhood leukaemias were identified in the HEMAP data. We initially set out to identify poor drug response, but in the follow-up genomic study we discovered the traits of leukaemia patients who respond well to drug treatments.”

One such sign of a good response is cells in the cell cycle. Cell life usually follows a rhythm – the cell cycle – in which cell division, i.e. mitosis, alternates with an intermediate phase, or interphase. The goal of the cell cycle is usually to produce two identical cells by cell division.

“By mapping individual cells, we determined the number of cells in the cycle. We were able to separate the different cells into phases, and the number of cells in the cycle seemed to be an important marker of a good response. Single-cell analysis is a good way to study how a cancer cell behaves. From there, the rarer surviving cells are revealed among the rest of the mass. It is important to study how drug treatment affects the cancer cell behaviour,” Heinäniemi says.

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) measures the activities of all genes in each cell separately, giving a more accurate view of cellular differences. This is important information, because cancer cells try to escape from immune cells by mutating.

“In cancer research, it is important to obtain data at the level of a single cell. The fact is that cancer cells change all the time, meaning that each cell begins to be different.”

HEMAP is real-time online interactive software for identifying and characterising different molecular phenotypes in various blood cancers. HEMAP contains 10,000 microarray profiles of different blood cancers. Haematopoiesis is a biological process by which the body produces new blood and maintains the defence system. Blood cells are formed through haematopoiesis from specialised stem cells in the bone marrow. HEMAP, hosted by CSC, now enables target gene analysis of drug molecules. A pilot version with single-cell precision measurement profiles also enables cell type identification. The image below shows the expression of the LCK oncogene in HEMAP samples – high level in red and low in blue. Lymphocyte-specific protein tyrosine kinase (LCK) is found at particularly high levels in T-cell acute leukaemia, which develops from T-lymphocytes. Mutations and high expression of LCK are associated with a wide range of diseases. Tyrosine kinases are enzymes whose defective regulation can contribute to the survival of myeloid leukaemia cells.

Now, single-cell technology for studying leukaemia can measure the profile of up to 10,000 cells in a single bone marrow sample. As single-cell technology becomes more common in cancer research, it will be easy to measure even millions of cells.

Preventing cancer cells from escaping during treatment

Heinäniemi's group in the research project found that leukaemia treatment rapidly triggers different kinds of escape pathways in cells by altering gene reading. This enables the cancer cell to evade the treatment given. The RNA molecular profiles that are read affect the construction of the functional part of the cell. In a way, this indicates the current state of the cell and what it is trying to do.

"A leukaemia cell is a type of bone marrow stem cell that still has the potential to change its phenotype. It can take on different phenotypes to try to hide from the treatment. For example, making the cell not divide so wildly is one escape route. During initial treatments, the cell can also switch between differentiation states and find a drug-resistant state."

In Heinäniemi's group, a broad molecular profile measured from cells can be

grouped using computational methods. This makes it possible to distinguish normal bone marrow cells from leukaemia cell profiles, and to identify different leukaemia cell phenotypes based on measurements. Models can also be trained to learn the relationship between different measurements collected from the same sample.

"The diagnostic stage does not fully reveal what kind of escape mechanisms those cancer cells may have. This is where single-cell technology has helped, because now we can measure those rare, resistant cell types during treatment. So we get new information, and we can then think about how we can prevent the cell from escaping, or find out where it is hiding."

Combining data from multiple sources

Now Heinäniemi's team has started to use the neural network models they have developed. Data is collected from different studies for this model.

"Our leukaemia project focuses on childhood cancers. It's a very rare type of cancer: if we don't get the data combined, the data sets will be very small. The aim is to use CSC's infrastructure for these

projects. This would allow the data to be processed and made available to the scientific community."

It is not possible to conduct a study using Finnish data only.

"We have a long history of Nordic collaboration. Now other European countries have also joined in. The aim would be to enable data provision for researchers who cannot process the data themselves. We bring together profiles that have already been collected and measured, because collecting them from public databases is laborious. The aim is to bring the single-cell data together in one place and in an accessible format. When we can bring the results of different research groups around the world together in one place, we can quickly compare which drug candidates might work."

Sharing data requires building trust. In practice, this means working with the patients involved in the projects.

"It's really important that they are involved and that their data is stored securely, and that researchers are able to do their work with the data. This is what CSC is enabling at national and EU level through its involvement in the ELIXIR infrastructure."

New information about cancer cells

Thanks to the new technology developed by SCellex, it is possible to determine from the tissue structure what type of cancer cells the tumour contains and whether a mutation, for example, has only affected a certain part of the tumour.

“Now we are able to find out accurately whether, for example, a tumour contains some cancer cells that are drug-resistant and what they are actually like,” says Saavalainen.

According to Saavalainen, immunotherapies for cancer have also developed dramatically. This works by helping the body’s own immune cells, T-cells, to identify and kill cancer cells. A T-cell is one of the two types of lymphocyte, along with the B-cell. They identify foreign structures and help kill cells infected by a virus and also cancer cells in which mutations have changed their own genome and consequently the proteins.

“Cancer cells are trying to escape from T-cells. They keep their changed structures hidden and secrete cytokines that silence T-cells. The goal with drug treatment is to allow T-cells to penetrate tissue, identify cancer cells aggressively and kill them. Now we are able to find out, for example, what a cancer cell next to a T-cell is doing. Is it creating some gene

product that silences the T-cell, and how is the T-cell reacting to that?”

According to Saavalainen, the best-case scenario is that we understand the cancer cell types of each patient and find an effective drug to which the patient responds well. This means we may be able to find means for individual treatments.

Spatial sequencing giving cell locations

Single-cell analytics is generally performed by gently separating the cells from the tissue and transferred individually into a solution, followed by sequencing of the RNA contained in them. However, the problem with this approach is that the original location of the cells and their order in the tissue will be lost, meaning we do not know which cells were originally next to each other. Thanks to modern spatial techniques, the cells no longer have to be separated in individual solutions; you simply slice layers only one cell in thickness from the tissue, with RNA obtained directly from such layers. As the RNA is sequenced, we know which cell and which part of the tissue the RNA originated from.

“This means we can sequence tissue and still know their location and maintain their original order. Spatial sequencing is one of the hottest things at the moment,” says Saavalainen.

ELIXIR Node of CSC has organised single-cell analytics courses for researchers, considers single-cell technology one of the most revolutionary methods in biosciences over the last few years.

“In cancer research, for example, it is important to obtain information about a single cell. The fact is that cancer cells change all the time, meaning that each cell begins to be different. There are also gene mutations, as a result of which certain genes are activated and others deactivated.”

Saavalainen considers single-cell resolution important also in the study of healthy tissues as we can find out what kind of cell types are found.

“Single-cell resolution has created a huge amount of new information for basic research alone. It was thought for a long time that humans have about 200 types of cell, but single-cell analyses have already identified more than 500.”

The locations of the cancer cell RNA-profiles in the tissue slice are determined with a machine learning model.

“The datasets are huge and the services of Finland ELIXIR Node of CSC can help to perform the computation.”

SCellex is developing a patented technology to determine the location of cells with machine learning models and microscopic colour beads. The beads are placed into a 160,000 picowell chip array platform and their random combinations create visual coordinates for the wells that can be calculated from the microscopic images by means of an AI model. The synthetic DNA codes attached to the microbeads are combined with the RNA molecules released from the tissue slices on the chip array platform, thereby linked to the well coordinates.

“We are using an AI model that can compute automatically which beads are in each well. In other words, AI creates a

map. After this the actual tissue section can be connected to the chip, after which the synthetic DNA strands glued to the colour beads are attached to the RNA from the tissue. The RNA molecules are attached to these strands and identification is made.”

“When RNA is sequenced in large batches, the data can be analysed to determine which colour bead combination the RNA matches, and then compare it with the original microscopic image and the AI computation. This way we can arrange the RNA data in their proper places.”

The datasets are huge and the services of Finland ELIXIR Node of CSC can help to perform the computation. Saavalainen says that the AI models are vital.

“If a sample contains tens of thousands of cells and all of them are subject to tens of thousands of gene measurement results, then not only the data on the microbeads but also the actual biological RNA data is immensely complex. You need AI to analyse it. AI can find such new information that simply would not be possible with traditional analysis tools. I think the computing power of CSC is sufficient even to solve our challenging AI models.”

Saavalainen says that the single-cell method is not yet mature enough to be used for diagnostics or prescription of drug treatments. However, at the moment it is a good tool for research purposes.

The AI model used for analysing microscopic images was developed with the software of Finnish company Aiforia Technologies.

GA4GH Passport

GA4GH Passport, a new international and open standard to encode machine-readable data access permissions for individual users.

Passports are used as part of a federated data regulatory process to authenticate and authorize data users in managing access to human biomedical datasets. Data access permissions (called “visas”) for individual users are issued by data stewards, including data access committees (DACs) working with public databases. The GA4GH Passport provides a standards to encode access permissions to data across repositories and

biomedical platforms powered by ELIXIR, such as ELIXIR Beacon Network (<https://beacon-network.elixir-europe.org>), with data provided by the EGA (European Genome-phenome Archive). Since its approval as a GA4GH standard in October 2019, the GA4GH Passport standard was adopted in three ecosystems: ELIXIR infrastructure in Europe and NIH in the United States. European experts played key roles in making the standard, and the work is currently one of the standards used in the Europe Genomic Data Infrastructure (<https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>).

Life Science Login (formerly ELIXIR AAI) is an identity and access management service portfolio used for authenticating data users and managing their access rights in services operated by ELIXIR and European e-Infrastructures. Life Science Login provides an implementation of a GA4GH Passport Broker (see Passport system components) that authenticates a data user and can retrieve ControlledAccess-Grants visas of the authenticated user from trusted source such as the EGA. GA4GH Passport standard for digital identity and access permissions. Cell Genomics Volume 1, Issue 2, 10 November 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100030>

YOUR ROLE
Identify your role in research data management and find relevant data management resources.

DATA LIFE CYCLE
Overview of research data management according to the stages of the data life cycle.

YOUR DOMAIN
Solutions to address the data management tasks that affect your domain or research community.

YOUR TASKS
Guidelines and solutions for common data management tasks.

The RDMkit website, created in cooperation with the ELIXIR nodes of the member countries, aims to support and harmonise data management practices in Europe. RDMkit includes instructions and tips concerning the entire life cycle of data – from data management planning and data analyses right up to publication and reuse.

ALL TRAINING RESOURCES
Training resources mentioned in RDMkit pages.

ALL TOOLS AND RESOURCES
RDMkit's tools and resources for research data management.

NATIONAL RESOURCES
Country specific information resources and research data management practices.

TOOL ASSEMBLY
Combinations of tools and resources in the ecosystem of research data management.

ELIXIR is a European life sciences infrastructure, bringing together scientists from 23 countries and over 250 research institutes.

Contact us at servicedesk@csc.fi Subject: "ELIXIR"

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